

Inherit

Active societal participation & enabling conditions for the INHERIT heritage-built environment/D2.2

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR/VR	Augmented Reality / Virtual Reality
BIVP	Building-integrated photovoltaics
CARTIF	Foundation CARTIF
CH	Cultural Heritage
D	Deliverable
ELLET	ELLINIKI ETAIREIA Society for the Environment and CH
FASADA	Przedsiębiorstwo Robót Elewacyjnych Fasada Sp. z o.o.
GA	Grant Agreement
GIS	Geographic Information System
H-BIM	Heritage Building Information Modelling
IBB	Izmir Metropolitan Municipality
IEQ	Indoor Environmental Quality
IoT	Internet of Things
MSF	Multi-Stakeholder Forum
NEB	New European Bauhaus
REGEA	Regional Energy Agency
RES	Renewable Energy Source
RPR	Riga Planning Region
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Analysis/Assessment
TCO	Thermal Comfort Optimisation
UU	Uppsala University
WP	Work Package

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ZSI

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Executive summary

The INHERIT project seeks to develop a systematic, innovative, and socially inclusive methodology for sustainable cultural heritage (CH) solutions. By integrating cutting-edge digital technologies, participatory models, and place-based interventions, the project aims to enhance the resilience, resource efficiency, and social value of CH buildings across diverse European contexts. A central aspect of the project's efforts is the engagement of stakeholders through co-creation and creative processes, ensuring that interventions reflect local needs and foster broad societal benefits.

This deliverable focuses on the social engagement dimension of INHERIT, reporting on principles and methodologies that guide participatory approaches in the heritage-built environment. It explores how the **New European Bauhaus (NEB) framework** serves as a catalyst for creative and community-driven placemaking and how enabling conditions allow inclusive and socially aware renovation strategies. It also introduces a **blueprint for co-creating user scenarios**, which will serve as a reference for designing and implementing CH solutions balancing the preservation of the buildings' heritage value with the much-needed renovations towards resource efficiency, resilience, and user comfort.

A key component of this deliverable is the **progress assessment of the INHERIT Social Labs** across seven pilot sites—Jastrebarsko (Croatia), Athens (Greece), Riga (Latvia), Gdynia (Poland), Valladolid (Spain), Visby (Sweden), and Izmir (Türkiye). Each Social Lab functions as a dynamic platform for co-creation, stakeholder interaction, and iterative feedback, ensuring transparent and trusted project interventions (see D2.1). Furthermore, this report examines the first results of the **Social Life Cycle Analysis (S-LCA)** in the context of the INHERIT project, evaluating how heritage-related interventions affect local stakeholders, heritage preservation, social acceptance, and participatory governance.

This deliverable represents an important milestone in the INHERIT project, reinforcing the commitment to participatory, socially inclusive, and sustainable CH management. It also provides an **overview of the next steps**, including the refinement of engagement strategies, the evolution of Social Labs, and the continued application of NEB values in CH initiatives. Through its work, INHERIT contributes to the broader European discourse on heritage sustainable renovation, testing how collaborative and technology-driven interventions can lead to more resilient, inclusive, and future-proof CH environments.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

The sustainable transformation of the heritage-built environment requires an inclusive and participatory approach that actively engages local stakeholders, integrates contemporary values, and fosters social innovation. CH plays a crucial role in shaping local identities, fostering community cohesion, and driving economic development. However, many heritage sites face challenges related to deterioration, underutilisation, energy inefficiency, and conflicts between conservation and contemporary urban needs. Addressing these issues requires a systematic approach that **balances preservation with adaptation**, ensuring that CH buildings remain relevant, accessible, and resilient in the face of climate change.

The INHERIT project, funded under the Horizon Europe programme, aims to **create next-generation solutions for sustainable, inclusive, and resource-efficient CH buildings**. These buildings, which vary significantly in age, construction methods, and architectural styles, present unique challenges that necessitate tailored approaches to ensure their preservation while adapting them to modern needs. The project's overarching goal is to address these challenges **by enhancing the sustainability of CH buildings while maintaining their cultural significance**. At the core of INHERIT's approach is the recognition that CH is not just a static entity to be preserved but an evolving space that must adapt to current circumstances and be actively shaped by and for its users. This means that heritage interventions must consider environmental sustainability, energy efficiency, digital innovation, and - very much so - social engagement. To achieve it, INHERIT embraces a multi-disciplinary framework integrating technological, scientific, and social layers (see Figure 1).

This deliverable, entitled ***Active societal participation & enabling conditions for the INHERIT heritage-built environment***, focuses in detail on the social engagement dimension of INHERIT by examining participatory approaches, stakeholder involvement, and enabling conditions that facilitate CH transformation.

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Figure 1: INHERIT methodology integrating societal, scientific, and technological processes

1.2. Relevant project’s tasks and activities

This deliverable builds upon previous work conducted within INHERIT, particularly under the WP2 in the areas of **co-creation, social innovation, and stakeholder engagement**. The main activities covered in this document focus on the enabling conditions that foster active societal participation in heritage conservation and energy efficiency. These activities include:

- the development and implementation of Social Labs, under Task 2.1 (**T2.1: Engagement strategy for participatory and co-creation processes**). These Labs function as experimental platforms for testing participatory methodologies in real-world pilot settings. They provide opportunities for stakeholders to co-create solutions that balance heritage renovation with modern needs;
- the application of Social Life Cycle Analysis (S-LCA), a tool designed to assess the social impacts of heritage interventions (**Task 2.2: Understanding heritage value to boost social impact and sustainability in the targeted CH sites**). This includes evaluating how different stakeholder groups perceive, engage with, and benefit from renovation efforts;
- the exploration of participatory frameworks and best practices, including strategies for integrating New European Bauhaus (NEB) values and working principles into heritage transformations (**Task 2.3: Social engagement, values and working principles for the INHERIT heritage-built environment**). This involves identifying methodologies that can enhance cultural accessibility, inclusivity, and long-term social benefits;
- the co-creation of the INHERIT solutions and user scenarios (**Task 2.4: Co-creating the INHERIT solutions and user scenarios**) to understand the needs, expectations, and experiences of stakeholders across the pilot sites to support the development of new technologies and services.

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Through these activities, INHERIT aims to establish a replicable model for participatory heritage management that can be adapted across different European contexts, ensuring a balance between the will to preserve and the need to adapt.

1.3. Objectives of the deliverable

The primary objective of this deliverable is to examine and document the key factors that enable active societal participation in the sustainable transformation of CH. Specifically, it seeks to:

- **identify enabling conditions** that facilitate meaningful stakeholder engagement and participatory governance in heritage conservation;
- **promote the role of social innovation and co-creation** in fostering sustainable and inclusive CH management, including the NEB initiative as framework for reimagining heritage spaces;
- **present insights from the INHERIT Social Labs**, showcasing how participatory methodologies have been implemented in pilot sites;
- **introduce the Social Life Cycle Analysis (S-LCA)** as a framework for assessing the broader social impact of heritage interventions, presenting the interim results from its application in pilot sites;
- **outline the future activities of the INHERIT project for co-creating social engagement**, including the expected outcomes of further Social Labs.

By addressing these objectives, this deliverable delineates the state of the art of INHERIT's efforts to activate societal participation in the transformation of its pilot heritage buildings. It may serve as a reference for policymakers, practitioners, and researchers aiming to develop socially responsive and innovative CH solutions.

1.4. Structure of the deliverable

After this first introductory chapter, this deliverable is structured into five consecutive sections. **Section 2** - Guiding principles for social engagement in INHERIT's heritage-built environment - draws **the foundational principles** guiding social engagement in the INHERIT project, emphasising the importance of co-creation, participatory approaches, and inclusive decision-making in heritage management.

The following sections delve deeper into project activities, providing insights on the methodology used and results achieved so far. **Section 3** presents an overview of **the progress of the INHERIT Social Labs**, detailing the methodologies used and the key takeaways from their implementation across INHERIT's pilot sites. **Section 4** introduces the first feedback loop in **the Social Life Cycle Analysis (S-LCA)** and the overview of preliminary findings of this key assessment tool.

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Next, **section 5 outlines the future activities** and co-creation strategies to boost social engagement further, including a first look into potential Lab Projects as concrete outcomes of the Social Labs. To conclude, **a final section synthesises the findings** of this report and provides a forward-looking perspective on how INHERIT will refine and expand societal participation in and out of the heritage-built environment.

2. Guiding principles for social engagement in INHERIT's heritage-built environment

The sustainable transformation of the heritage-built environment requires a socially engaged and inclusive approach that aligns with contemporary values and participatory models. As such, this section establishes the foundational principles guiding social engagement in the project, ensuring that CH interventions prioritise equality, accessibility, and long-term social benefits.

Renovating with a social focus means that restoration and adaptation processes and interventions actively consider user comfort, community needs, and a broader social well-being, as well as affordability and economic sustainability. The project integrates **participatory models** that empower local stakeholders to contribute to decision-making, fostering collaboration and a sense of ownership. Additionally, the [New European Bauhaus \(NEB\) initiative](#) serves as a key framework, linking aesthetics, sustainability, and togetherness to reimagine the heritage-built environment in creative and inspiring ways.

Participatory models and NEB values are embedded in the co-designing and co-creating processes of the INHERIT project. **Co-creating user scenarios** is an essential component for the project to address real-world challenges. It enables INHERIT to foster a socially sustainable transformation of the heritage-built environment based on the needs, expectations, and experiences of local stakeholders and service users.

2.1. Renovating with a social focus

Energy-efficient renovations of heritage or historic buildings are not just technical upgrades to buildings; they are part of a broader transformation that integrates **social, cultural, and environmental factors**. As the world faces the climate crisis, it becomes critical to approach energy renovations holistically, considering not only energy-saving technologies but also the preservation of CH and the resilience of local communities. This intersection is where **societal enablers**—factors that shape how society accepts and implements these changes—come into play. To achieve this comprehensive goal, INHERIT establishes **a systematic methodology** for sustainable, inclusive, and resource-efficient CH solutions. This approach integrates social, scientific, and technological processes, generating outcomes across all three dimensions. In particular, the **social processes** - incorporating social sciences, a multi-stakeholder approach, and co-creation - ensure that the technological outcomes, such as 11 digital services, Internet of Things (IoT), Augmented and Virtual Reality, Digital twins, as well as scientific developments like the Assessment & Monitoring

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Framework and the Hub of Measures, are framed within a **socially centred renovation strategy**, respectful of CH and local identity.

2.1.1. CH and climate resilience in EU programmes

The European Union (EU) has spearheaded several initiatives aimed at fostering sustainable development while respecting CH, particularly under **Horizon 2020** and, more recently, under **Horizon Europe**, the EU's largest research and innovation programmes. The INHERIT project itself is funded under Horizon Europe. Both programmes have dedicated significant resources to projects that address how CH can contribute to resilient, energy-efficient, and affordable renovations and climate adaptation, emphasising the need for inclusive and community-driven approaches.

Horizon 2020 funded numerous projects aimed at addressing the climate crisis through innovations that respect and preserve Europe's vast CH. These projects serve as important references in illustrating how societal enablers can facilitate energy-efficient renovations while safeguarding **local identity and traditions**.

- [CLIC \(Circular Models Leveraging Investments in Cultural Heritage Adaptive Reuse\)](#): This project promotes the **adaptive reuse** of CH as a key solution for sustainable development and energy efficiency. It explores how **circular economy models** can revitalise historical buildings, making them energy-efficient while retaining their cultural significance. CLIC emphasises the **social dimension** by engaging local communities in decision-making processes, ensuring that the adaptive reuse of heritage sites reflects local needs and values;
- [ROCK \(Regeneration and Optimisation of Cultural Heritage in Creative and Knowledge Cities\)](#): ROCK focuses on transforming **historic city centers** through sustainable innovation while preserving CH. It supports **energy-efficient renovations** in culturally rich areas by leveraging **green technologies** in conjunction with social and economic revitalisation strategies. ROCK demonstrates how cities can remain resilient during the climate crisis by integrating heritage preservation with energy-efficient urban planning.

CLIC, ROCK, and similar projects highlight how incorporating societal values, CH, and local stakeholder engagement into building renovation and retrofitting for energy optimisation ensures that communities not only accept but actively support and benefit from climate-responsive measures.

These projects build on a **rich legacy of initiatives** under various EU programmes, such as the 7th Framework Programme (FP7) and Interreg, which have already emphasised the need for resilience in the face of the climate crisis. They recognised that **preserving CH** is not at odds with achieving energy efficiency but rather complements it. A few key examples include:

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- [HeritageCare \(Management and Monitoring System for Preventive Conservation of Historical and Cultural Buildings\)](#): A project aimed at implementing systems for the **preventive conservation** of historic buildings, using innovative technologies and energy-efficient methods to ensure **long-term sustainability**. It promotes **community-based monitoring** and management systems, ensuring that local stakeholders are involved in the process of heritage conservation and energy optimisation;
- [Climate for Culture](#): Although developed during the Horizon 2020 programme, this project continues to influence the Horizon Europe agenda. It explores the impact of climate change on Europe's CH and develops adaptation strategies for historic buildings. The focus is on improving the **energy performance** of these sites without compromising their **historical integrity**, offering solutions for making heritage buildings more resilient to climate stress while enhancing their energy efficiency.

These initiatives demonstrate that heritage and innovation are not only compatible but mutually reinforcing in the pursuit of resilience to the climate crisis. At the same time, the success of these projects underscores the need for **participatory models**, where local communities are engaged as active stakeholders in the adaptation processes. The next section explores how such models can further enhance the potential of CH preservation in the face of climate change.

2.2. Participatory models in heritage-built environment

As the climate crisis continues to reshape our approach to urban and rural development, the role of CH in **the built environment must evolve** to reflect both the preservation of local identity and the need for sustainability. This is not an easy task: energy-efficient renovations often meet resistance when they are perceived as conflicting with local values or with the preservation of historical sites. However, INHERIT and the initiatives presented above highlight the importance of **engaging local communities** in the adaptation and retrofitting of CH sites. They demonstrate that **societal enablers** - factors that help local populations, policymakers, and cultural institutions accept and participate in these projects - can **bridge the gap** between **heritage conservation** and **modern energy standards**. These societal enablers play a critical role in fostering acceptance and engagement, making the renovation process not only about energy efficiency but also about preserving and harmonising with the cultural identity.

In this regard, **participatory models**, which emphasise the involvement of local communities in decision-making processes, are increasingly seen as key to achieving objectives in the context of **heritage preservation** and **climate adaptation**. These models are not just theoretical ideals but a practical necessity in creating climate-resilient and energy-efficient heritage sites. The growing recognition of societal enablers - factors such as community involvement, local knowledge, and cultural values - is central to understanding how participatory approaches can enhance the preservation and transformation of heritage buildings. Participatory models in heritage

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conservation go beyond consultation to **actively involve stakeholders at every stage** of the process, from planning and design to implementation and management. In doing so, they address both **social sustainability** and **cultural resilience**, ensuring that preservation or renovation efforts align with the needs and priorities of the community. These models allow for the co-creation of solutions that reflect the historical and cultural significance of heritage sites while simultaneously leveraging on innovative techniques for energy optimisation and climate resilience.

We have seen the benefits of participatory models in past initiatives, which constitute a pool of knowledge and a fertile ground for INHERIT. For example, projects like **CLIC** and **ROCK** underlined the importance of **involving communities in decision-making processes** from the start. This ensures that renovations are not seen as imposed from outside but are embraced as a way to both preserve local identity and adapt to new energy needs. Local stakeholders, including citizens, cultural institutions, and businesses, should be part of the co-creation process. The **HeritageCare** project applied **community-based monitoring** and **management systems** to ensure the long-term sustainability of historic buildings. By enabling local stakeholders to take part in the conservation and energy optimisation processes, the project fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility, thus enhancing the overall effectiveness of preservation efforts. **Climate for Culture**, which continues to influence ongoing projects under Horizon Europe, emphasised the importance of **community-driven climate adaptation strategies** for heritage buildings. It recognises that preserving CH is not only about maintaining physical structures but also about protecting the community's connection to its history and identity. Participatory models make it possible for these connections to thrive while addressing the challenges posed by the climate crisis.

INHERIT, for its part, builds on this knowledge and adopts a **multi-stakeholder approach** to engage stakeholders in co-planning the renovation of CH buildings. The project includes various actions to assess the social acceptance of proposed interventions to identify the most appropriate solutions from a range of measures and digital services. One of the pillars of the **Assessment & Monitoring Framework** evaluates improvements in accessibility, inclusiveness, and openness at pilot sites, and a **Social Science Framework** will be used to define cost-effective and viable solutions for the renovation of heritage buildings. Additionally, measures are taken to **educate the public** and **raise awareness** about the benefits of energy-efficient renovations that respect CH, as well as the importance of protecting and preserving heritage buildings. In this respect, **e-learning packages** and **webinars** for a wide public will be provided. This educational dimension is particularly important in fostering a community perspective that sees energy-efficient renovations not as a threat to CH but as a means of adapting it to contemporary needs, making heritage more resilient in the face of climate change. Furthermore, **policy dialogues** will be facilitated to ensure that the stakeholder needs are acknowledged, while **outreach activities** prepare the ground for replication and upscaling of results.

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In conclusion, participatory models play a critical role in ensuring that energy-efficient renovations are successful, especially in culturally significant areas. Lessons from Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects demonstrate that **CH can be preserved and even enhanced during the energy transition**. Achieving this requires strong community engagement, policy support, and financial incentives to ensure renovations are both technically sound and socially accepted. Alongside INHERIT in this goal, the **NEB framework** provides powerful support for a sustainable, inclusive and heritage-aware transformation.

2.3. New European Bauhaus (NEB) as enabling framework

The **New European Bauhaus (NEB)** initiative is a creative and interdisciplinary movement launched by the European Commission that promotes sustainable, inclusive, and aesthetically pleasing living environments. At project level, within INHERIT, the NEB approach accelerates the **integration of aesthetic and functional aspects** in the renovation of historic buildings, creating spaces that are inclusive and beautiful as well as more sustainable. The NEB also serves as a bridge between the world of science and technology, art and culture - an interdisciplinary perspective that is essential when moving **beyond the mere conservation** of heritage sites toward **innovative management and reuse**. This ensures that heritage spaces are adapted to contemporary needs while safeguarding their cultural significance.

The **INHERIT Social Labs** (see Section 3) well exemplify this approach by bringing together diverse local stakeholders, such as citizens, heritage experts, social scientists, businesses, urban planners, and institutions, to foster a **multidisciplinary dialogue**. This dialogue merges the technical, social, and cultural aspects of the renovation process. As such, the NEB framework serves as a **key enabler** in reimagining and transforming the heritage-built environment, under the INHERIT project and beyond: it provides a **new powerful tool** for socially engaged and culturally invested renovators. Within INHERIT, the NEB framework acts as a **catalyst for built-heritage innovation** and a guide for:

- promoting participatory processes that engage local communities in decision-making;
- ensuring energy-efficient retrofitting while preserving historical integrity;
- encouraging adaptive reuse of CH buildings, with emphasis on user comfort;
- connecting CH sites with their outdoor surroundings and natural spaces;
- strengthening the sense of belonging by integrating cultural values into urban transformations.

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This **inspirational framework** is articulated around **three core values**: togetherness (at times also called ‘inclusion’), sustainability, and beauty, which stand as a single, guiding ‘polar star’. However, the polar star is not meant to remain up in the air but must be brought down to the ground and translated into practical action through **three operational principles**: participatory process, multi-level engagement, and transdisciplinary approach (see Figure 2). The [NEB compass](#) is the key reference document for aligning projects with the NEB framework. Conversely, all three NEB values **align with INHERIT’s mission** and find valid applications within the project.

Figure 2: NEB values and working principles

Firstly, the project purpose of retrofitting and adapting heritage buildings aligns with the value ‘**togetherness**’ as INHERIT contributes to **strengthening community-led governance models** for heritage sites and facilitating co-creation workshops, such as the Social Labs, to involve diverse stakeholders in decision-making. The project also promotes heritage renovations able to **foster accessibility and openness**, ensuring that spaces are welcoming regardless of gender, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, ability, age or sexual orientation.

Secondly, the project pursues ‘**sustainability**’ by encouraging **low-carbon renovations** and supporting **energy-efficient retrofitting** that respects heritage buildings while reducing their environmental footprint. Under the project, eleven technologically advanced services are being developed with the explicit intent of facilitating decision-making for the renovation of heritage buildings, helping stakeholders achieve the **optimal balance** between cost, energy efficiency, resilience, and user well-being.

Thirdly, INHERIT embraces the NEB understanding of ‘**beauty**’ - which extends beyond aesthetics to include emotional, sensory, and experiential dimensions of CH. The project promotes **high-quality architectural interventions** that respect historical aesthetics and cultural values. The designed solutions aim to go beyond mere functionality and improve **user perception and emotional engagement**, enhancing CH as a living experience.

On top of that, the NEB serves both as a **policy and financial enabler**, bridging the European Green Deal vision with targeted local investments that yield measurable impacts. The [NEB Investments](#)

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[Guidelines](#) provide structured recommendations to help translate NEB values and principles into practice, emphasising place-based approaches, inclusive design, and long-term planning. A key financial mechanism is the [NEB Facility](#), a dedicated multiannual financial support instrument under the Horizon Europe programmes 2025-2027. Additionally, [NEB prizes and grants](#) incentivise best practices and reduce the financial burden on municipalities and local communities looking to retrofit historic buildings to modern energy standards through socially conscious renovations.

For all the reasons above, NEB constitutes an enabling framework, a transformative tool for INHERIT. Recognising its importance in and for the project, **two online events** have been organised within INHERIT to raise awareness among partners and interested parties. Similarly, as part of the second round of Social Labs, **in-person activities** were organised at local level to examine the integration of sustainability, accessibility, and aesthetics in the renovation of the INHERIT pilot heritage buildings. By embracing the **NEB as an enabling framework**, INHERIT fosters a holistic approach to heritage conservation, paving the way for heritage-built transformations that are **environmentally responsible, socially inclusive, and aesthetically inspiring**.

2.3.1. NEB online and in-person workshops in INHERIT project

As anticipated, two online events have been held to engage project partners and stakeholders in NEB thinking. The first event, titled **NEB values for change in CH**, was a closed session for project partners. It aimed to develop compelling **local narratives on CH**, using them **as entry points for transformation**. The session showcased examples of redoing heritage by recognising hidden assets and aligning ambitions with the NEB values. It included a keynote presentation on NEB values, brief stories about the connections to local heritage sites in the form of video messages, and case studies exemplifying NEB values in practice. Specifically, the [NEB local initiatives](#) of Alūksne and Cēsis (Latvia), as well as the FIAB project in the Azores Islands (Portugal) were presented. The meeting continued with an open floor for participants to discuss how they could initiate their own story of change. The reflection was guided by this query: ‘the beauty of inclusive renovation of historic buildings towards energy efficiency lies in...’. Among the many responses, we list a few examples:

- user acceptance;
- engaging and connecting new stakeholders;
- otherness;
- using NBS Nature-based solutions, not only for exteriors but also for the interiors;
- a balance between modern solutions and the preservation of historical values;
- the beauty of the ‘ugly’, i.e. industrial heritage;
- the sense of belonging.

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The second event was open to a broader audience and functioned as the kick-off for the [INHERIT Multi-Stakeholder Forum \(MSF\)](#). The MSF is based on three pillars supporting CH: NEB values, social responsibility & inclusion, and green technology (see Figure 3). The kick-off event, titled *Thinking out-of-the-box with New European Bauhaus for CH buildings (management and policy making)*,

Figure 3: Three pillars of the INHERIT Multi-Stakeholder Forum

focused on the role of the NEB in leading sustainable change, highlighting the practical value and the impact of the NEB on CH and retrofit initiatives.

The first part of the event showcased good practices from Central and Eastern Europe, exploring innovative actions such as the European project [LIFE Bauhausing Europe](#), the INHERIT pilot project in Jastrebarsko (Croatia), and the NEB Prize-winning project [Re-sourcing commons](#) in Wien (Austria). The second part opened with an interactive ‘open mic’ session inviting participants to share their reflections and experiences related to NEB, CH, and retrofit, renovation, and replanning projects. Academics and NEB experts also presented their insights on the subject.

In addition to these online events, **in-person workshops were featured in seven pilot areas** during the second round of Social Labs as part of the INHERIT commitment to integrating the NEB framework. The overall aim was **to explore how sustainability, inclusivity, and aesthetics can be applied to heritage renovation**. The mockup of the activities, flexible and adaptable to local contexts, suggested a short introduction to NEB values and working principles, followed by an icebreaking exercise to explore the NEB ‘flower’ (see Figure 1) and get familiar with the NEB concepts. For example, participants could note down words that they associate to the values, breaking down these complex concepts into more immediate or more accessible components. For the core part of the meeting, the project activities, actions, or initiatives - pre-listed by the facilitator – were reflected upon to **identify obstacles** in their implementation **and find compatible solutions**. The first question guiding the discussion was about obstacles that did or could slow down specific INHERIT activities, actions, or initiatives and reduce their impact; the second guiding question aimed to identify what could be the enabling conditions in the pilot area, and what could help gain local buy-in.

Below, figure 4 shows the Polish version of the guiding questions:

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- What are the enabling social factors for INHERIT in our pilot area?
- What are the challenges in engaging the community and stakeholders in the life of the pilot building?

Figure 4: Workshop's guiding questions

At this stage, the words found during the icebreaker could guide participants toward NEB-like solutions. One of the recurring themes across workshops was the **low initial awareness of the NEB** initiative, as seen in Gdynia (Poland) where only four out of eighteen participants had previously encountered it. This gap was addressed through interactive presentations and exercises, such as the NEB flower model, which helped participants familiarise themselves with the NEB values in a visual way and explore how heritage buildings could embody them. Stakeholders across multiple sessions, including those facilitated in Valladolid (Spain), Riga (Latvia), and Izmir (Türkiye), engaged in **interdisciplinary discussions on balancing sustainability with CH restrictions**.

In Karlovac (Croatia) participants in a collaborative event of the INHERIT and [SMART DeCARB](#) projects took this further by extending NEB principles beyond individual buildings to broader energy transition initiatives, discussing strategies for **integrating sustainability and inclusiveness into public building decarbonisation**. Similarly, in Athens's (Greece) workshop, discussions revolved around co-designing technical solutions that promote resilience, energy efficiency, and long-term sustainability in heritage sites. In Visby (Sweden), the NEB national contact point opened the discussion on how Visby's built heritage could contribute to sustainable urban development.

Furthermore, the workshops also highlighted the **importance of social factors** in the success of NEB-driven renovations. Across different locations, participants identified key challenges such as **legal and financial barriers to resident engagement**. For example, in Gdynia (Poland), stakeholders discussed how issues like property ownership restrictions and financial difficulties hinder

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community participation. Proposed solutions focused on transparency, education, and incentive structures that would empower residents and ensure both financial and social security.

These NEB-focused activities have been held **as part of the second round of the INHERIT Social Labs** - local workshops that integrate different perspectives and foster interdisciplinary dialogue, laying the groundwork for more participative and co-created interventions for a resilient and inclusive heritage-built environment. Further below, section 3 of this deliverable presents the progress and current status of the INHERIT Social Labs.

2.4. Blueprint for co-creating user scenarios

Participatory models and NEB values are embedded in the co-designing and co-creating processes of the INHERIT project. As part of the development of INHERIT eleven services - innovative solutions for smart management of historic building efficiency - **co-creating user scenarios** is essential to shape these services in the most meaningful way. To ensure these solutions effectively address real-world challenges, it is crucial **to understand the needs, expectations, and experiences of key stakeholders** across the pilot sites. A key part of this process is identifying user stories, which describe how different users interact with a service to achieve their goals. Scenarios are commonly used to illustrate potential outcomes and play a key role in gathering user requirements. They help generate ideas, identify user needs, explore different ways technologies can be used, and support the development of new technologies and services (Sasse, 2006).

The methodology that is followed by the co-design of the INHERIT solutions is divided into three phases (see Figure 5).

- **Phase 1:** Collection of User Stories;
- **Phase 2:** Co-design of User-friendly Environments;
- **Phase 3:** Refinement of Usability.

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Figure 5: The three phases of INHERIT’s co-creation of services

This division into three phases is designed to ensure a comprehensive analysis of user needs, enabling us to create solutions that are as user-friendly as possible. By breaking down the process, we can pay close attention to detail at every stage - **gathering insights from users, co-designing intuitive environments, and continuously refining the usability of the solutions** based on real feedback. This approach allows for iterative improvements, ensuring that the final solutions not only meet the users' needs but also enhance their overall experience, making them practical and accessible. The description offered below covers phase 1 and phase 2, while phase 3 will start later in the project and has not yet been developed.

2.4.1. Phase 1: Collection of User Stories

The first phase, **‘Collection of User Stories’** encompassed the first year of the project. Detailed information about this phase and the corresponding workshop can be found in D2.1.

Following the completion of the first workshop, the results were analysed alongside internally identified user requirements, leading to their consolidation. During this process, it was observed that several **internally identified requirements aligned with the needs of the stakeholders** who participated in the workshop. In this initial phase, the stakeholder group primarily consisted of engineers, developers, and IT experts, as the workshop's primary goal was to refine and validate the technical user requirements.

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2.4.2. Phase 2: Co-design of User-friendly Environments

The second phase of the co-creation of the services covers most part of the project's second year. The **'Co-design of User-friendly Environments'** focuses on transforming initial user requirements into more concrete, structured representations. During this phase, service providers developed user flow diagrams to map out the interactions and processes within their services. These diagrams helped visualise how different users engage with the services, highlighting possible user journeys.

To ensure clarity and accessibility, service providers also prepared supporting materials that illustrated these flows through wireframes, and mock-ups. These visualisations played a crucial role in **communicating design concepts to stakeholders**, making it easier for them to understand, evaluate, and provide feedback (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Screenshots from the second workshop for the co-design of services

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The development of these materials laid the groundwork for the co-design workshop, where stakeholders were invited to review and assess the proposed service flows. The primary goal of the workshop was to gather **feedback on the users' experience** and identify any potential gaps or areas for improvement. Feedback from the workshop's participants was gathered through structured discussions and closed-ended questions.

A key takeaway was **the importance of high-quality visualization in AR/VR environments**. Participants emphasised that detailed rendering of textures and structures is essential for accurate renovation planning, while real-time AR data overlays should display critical structural and renovation information. For maintenance, simplified visualisations focusing on key structural elements were preferred. Moreover, participants confirmed that the simulation model aligns with the historic preservation guidelines relevant to them and supports energy efficiency improvements without compromising CH. They also appreciated the **cost-benefit analyses for retrofitting measures**, which helps decision-making on energy-saving interventions.

Key renovation planning criteria were identified, including non-energy benefits like thermal comfort and CO₂ reduction, alongside social aspects such as preserving historical value and improving accessibility. Economic considerations, including long-term energy savings and lifecycle cost analysis, were also highlighted. **Structural resilience, heritage preservation, and energy efficiency were deemed critical** for sustainable renovations.

Next, the evaluation of the Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) and Thermal Comfort Optimisation (TCO) tool showed that real-time tracking and historical analysis provide valuable insights for **improving occupant comfort** while ensuring compliance with preservation requirements. Participants found its data visualisation to be intuitive and its energy optimisation strategies practical. Most people preferred an end-of-week forecasting window and suggested adding a feature to highlight optimisation process durations for better planning.

For **digital twin technology**, participants requested a pathology monitoring module for tracking humidity, CO, and CO₂ levels. They also suggested **enhancing preventive maintenance** with expense projections and an advanced alarm system for humidity, CO concentration, and water leaks. For **maintenance management and H-BIM integration**, stakeholders proposed automating maintenance notifications, tracking overdue inspections, and scheduling preventive maintenance with predefined thresholds. They also suggested integrating indoor air quality monitoring and material tracking. Facades, roofs, and CH assets were identified as top priorities for maintenance.

Finally, regarding the **monitoring visitor flow**, presence sensors were favoured over cameras, with a preference for real-time and on-demand access to activity data. Participants recommended

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incorporating advanced statistical insights, heat maps, and summary statistics to track trends in visitor density and crowding events.

More detailed results generated from the second workshop on the co-creation of services will be provided in D2.3, expected for February 2026, along with the interim results of the third phase.

3. Progress of the INHERIT Social Labs

One of the most important tools to operationalise participative models, New European Bauhaus (NEB) values, and co-creation processes are **the INHERIT Social Labs**. The Social Labs are designed as collaborative spaces where stakeholders from science, innovation, CH practice and civil society come together to address complex challenges related to CH. These Labs focus on mutual learning in an experimental environment, where diverse individuals or organisations with a shared interest in the objectives of INHERIT **work together to develop and test solutions**. The Labs allow for transdisciplinary interventions and social experiments, enabling the testing of prototypes in real-world social settings, which promotes the uptake of results. The following sub-chapters summarised and analysed the documentation materials from the kick-off and the second round of the Social Labs, which have already taken place in INHERIT pilot sites, namely:

- City Administration Headquarters in Jastrebarsko (Croatia), represented by REGEA;
- ELLET building in Tripodon street in Athens (Greece), represented by ELLET;
- Ave sol concert hall in Riga (Latvia), represented by RPR;
- Social residential building in Gdynia (Poland), represented by FASADA;
- Monastery 'Ntra. Sra. del Prado' in Valladolid (Spain), represented by CARTIF;
- City of Visby (Sweden), represented by UU;
- Ahmet Piriştina İzmir City Archive and Museum in Izmir (Turkey), represented by IBB.

3.1. Jastrebarsko – Croatia | REGEA

3.1.1. Results of the Social Labs kick-off event

REGEA's Social Labs kick-off event, held at the Center for Culture in Jastrebarsko, brought together 14 participants from diverse stakeholder groups to discuss the integration of **NEB values - sustainability, togetherness, and aesthetics** - into urban development, with a specific focus on the pilot building in Jastrebarsko. Structured activities included introductions to the NEB values, presentations on CH buildings, and group discussions to identify needs, potentials, and constraints for the pilot site and surrounding urban areas. The primary objective was to foster innovative approaches to CH revitalisation and promote collaboration among stakeholders.

Participants included public authorities, educational institutions, cultural and creative industries, civil society organisations, and urban planners, who provided valuable input on potential uses for the pilot building, such as addressing the need for administrative space and a city library. Discussions highlighted the importance of broader stakeholder engagement, including citizens and companies like *Hrvatske ceste* (Croatian Roads), and proposed solutions for urban planning challenges, such as

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transforming the pedestrian-unfriendly **state of road D1** – a main road running right in front of the pilot building.

Key findings underscored the need for **accessible, sustainable and inclusive urban planning**, addressing significant barriers like the state road D1 and the functional deficiencies of the administration building, including inadequate workspaces and poor heating systems. Constraints such as limited financing, conservation restrictions and political challenges were identified as critical issues to address for the project's success.

Future activities proposed by participants include integrating Social Labs with larger public events to enhance community involvement and communication. **A mapping walk provided insights into the city's CH** and reinforced the importance of balancing historical preservation with innovative urban solutions. The project emphasises social innovation by fostering collaboration between public authorities, cultural groups and citizens to ensure inclusive decision-making in heritage building renovations. By aligning with NEB values and REGEA's vision for sustainable revitalisation, the workshop laid a foundation for transforming the pilot building into a model for future development.

3.1.2. Results of the second Social Lab event

The second social Lab workshop of REGEA took place on 5 December 2024 in Karlovac, Croatia, as part of the SMART DeCARB conference. Stakeholders from Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Montenegro **discussed decarbonising public buildings while preserving CH**. The workshop focused on integrating New European Bauhaus values—sustainability, aesthetics and inclusiveness—into energy transition initiatives. Participants explored how to balance heritage conservation with modern energy solutions, implement smart monitoring and decision-support tools and strengthen cross-border collaboration. They concluded the event by planning pilot tests for INHERIT solutions in selected municipalities.

In the first module, participants examined how to apply NEB values to historic building decarbonisation. A pre-workshop questionnaire showed that while stakeholders understood sustainability, they were less familiar with NEB values. An interactive session introduced these principles through case studies. Discussions covered sustainability, aesthetics and inclusiveness, focusing on renewable energy integration, financial and regulatory barriers and solutions such as EU green financing and public-private partnerships. Attendees emphasised the need for architectural guidelines aligned with NEB principles and proposed using **Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV) and modern heat pumps**. To address community engagement and public resistance, they recommended interactive workshops and awareness campaigns. Key challenges included regulatory restrictions, technical limitations, and financial constraints. Participants proposed policy adaptations, innovative technologies like adaptive insulation and BIPV and financial incentives such as EU grants and tax benefits. Next steps involve public engagement strategies, technical assessments and integrating smart monitoring.

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The second module introduced digital tools and decision-support frameworks for optimising energy interventions in heritage buildings. **Stakeholders explored INHERIT services**, including a real-time monitoring platform, a decision-support tool for renovation strategies, an IEQ tool and a climate scenario assessment tool. They highlighted decision-support tools as essential for municipalities selecting sustainable renovations and stressed the importance of smart monitoring and climate impact assessments for resilience planning. To enhance engagement, they proposed using visual reports, digital dashboards, and AR/VR tools. They also underscored the importance of predictive maintenance data for the long-term sustainability of historical structures. Next steps involve implementing smart monitoring in pilot buildings, testing climate impact models and refining decision-support frameworks in collaboration with conservation experts.

The workshop concluded with a group discussion. Representatives from Karlovac, Bihać, and Jastrebarsko expressed strong interest in piloting INHERIT solutions within their municipalities. They reaffirmed **a data-driven approach to sustainable energy transitions in heritage buildings**. Participants committed to implementing pilot projects, strengthening cross-border cooperation, engaging policymakers and the public through digital tools and refining technical guidelines. The next phase will translate discussions into actionable steps, ensuring pilot projects serve as replicable models. Findings will contribute to policy recommendations, technical guidelines and strategic funding applications to scale sustainable energy solutions in heritage buildings.

3.2. Athens – Greece | ELLET

3.2.1. Results of the Social Labs kick-off event

ELLET's social Lab kick-off event, held in the organisation's building in Athens, launched discussions on enhancing the **energy performance of historical buildings** while preserving their architectural identity. Structured around a welcome coffee, a building tour, project introduction and rotating table discussions, the event focused on stakeholder needs, energy retrofitting challenges and regulatory constraints. The session concluded with an analysis of regulatory and technical barriers to achieving energy efficiency in heritage contexts.

16 stakeholders from diverse sectors participated, including end-users, building owners, policymakers, researchers, energy providers, and engineers. However, critical groups such as CH officers, energy auditors, and local authority representatives were absent. Participants gained insights into optimising building energy performance, navigating regulatory complexities, and promoting the importance of energy-efficient renovations within their networks. **Community involvement and civil society advocacy emerged as vital** for prioritising sustainable heritage conservation.

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Key challenges identified included complex bureaucratic procedures, insufficient training for public inspection bodies, policy conflicts between conservation and energy goals, a lack of standardised renovation guidelines, and high retrofitting costs. The event highlighted the necessity of bridging **gaps between policymakers and technical experts** and addressing the financial barriers to incentivise renovations.

Insights from the discussions emphasised the importance of early community engagement, transparent communication, and involving policymakers to streamline the approval process. Participants expressed willingness to remain involved, though scheduling constraints were noted. Future Social Labs will explore online formats to increase participation and will focus on sensor data analysis from the pilot building, scalability of solutions, and addressing unique challenges in areas housing antiquities. The project aligns closely with **NEB values of sustainability, togetherness, and aesthetics**, as confirmed by participants. The pilot building aims to serve as a model for balancing energy efficiency, architectural preservation, and innovation. Continued stakeholder engagement, addressing training and regulatory gaps, and leveraging ELLET's network to disseminate findings are key to advancing sustainable heritage management across Greece.

3.2.2. Results of the second Social Lab event

The second social Lab workshop took place on December 16, 2024, at the ELLET pilot building in Athens, focusing on challenges and opportunities in CH conservation. The discussions **centred on technical solutions for energy efficiency, resilience and sustainability**, bringing together public authorities, policymakers, academics, architects and private sector professionals.

The workshop followed a structured format, beginning with a panel discussion on contemporary challenges in heritage conservation. Experts explored topics such as energy-efficient renovation, policy frameworks, and financial mechanisms that support conservation efforts. The second session, **'Ellet Cafés'**, allowed participants to engage in thematic discussions on **institutional and financial frameworks, soft interventions, active systems, and user comfort and inclusivity**. The final session summarised key insights and conclusions.

Several barriers to sustainable heritage conservation were identified, including financial constraints, strict regulatory requirements, and the complexities of integrating modern energy systems into historic buildings. The need for public-private partnerships, financial incentives for energy-efficient renovations, and the adoption of smart technologies for real-time monitoring and maintenance were emphasised.

The second module of the workshop introduced technical services and assessment pillars within the INHERIT project. Stakeholders explored the role of **Digital Twins** in simulating energy performance and structural behaviour, aiding renovation planning. Discussions covered **IoT sensors and Machine Learning algorithms** for monitoring temperature, humidity, and air quality, with

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participants recognising their potential for optimising energy consumption and enhancing user comfort. Survey results highlighted **IEQ & Comfort Optimisation** and **Energy Forecasting & Data-Driven Intelligence Management** as the most valuable services for the ELLET pilot building, addressing issues such as poor insulation, high humidity, and fluctuating indoor conditions. The highest-rated assessment pillar was Resource Efficiency, Circularity & Life Cycle Costs, while Resilience to Climate and Human-Made Hazards received the lowest rating.

The discussions also underscored the value of **H-BIM models** in cataloguing necessary repairs, improving renovation planning, and supporting preventive maintenance. The integration of smart energy systems was seen as beneficial for reducing operational costs and enhancing sustainability goals. The workshop concluded with the establishment of a **10-point guide for sustainable conservation**, recommending strengthened institutional frameworks, climate-adaptive interventions, categorisation of historic buildings based on intervention needs and the integration of advanced monitoring technologies. The importance of interdisciplinary collaboration was highlighted, encouraging cooperation between engineers, architects, policymakers and conservation specialists.

Next steps include conducting an analysis of the ELLET pilot surrounding urban area, developing a conservation strategy based on stakeholder recommendations and engaging key actors in the implementation phase. **The findings will inform future INHERIT initiatives**, ensuring best practices in energy-efficient heritage conservation are widely adopted while balancing sustainability, user comfort and historical integrity. A key outcome of the Lab Project, one of the outputs of the Social Labs, will be organising brief presentations by experts and key stakeholders followed by a collaborative workshop with students under their guidance.

3.3. Riga – Latvia | RPR

3.3.1. Results of the Social Labs kick-off event

The kick-off of the Social Labs event organised by the Riga Planning Region (RPR), brought together seventeen participants to discuss **energy efficiency in CH buildings**, aiming to provide methodological support to municipalities. The event focused on **sustainable solutions that balance energy efficiency with cultural preservation**, highlighting technical and financial challenges associated with renovating CH buildings. Held at the Riga Council, the workshop facilitated open discussions and fostered collaboration among stakeholders, including Riga city officials, policymakers, NGOs, professional associations, and heritage owners. However, the absence of some invited participants underscored the need for improved outreach and engagement strategies.

Key insights included the importance of preparatory work with stakeholders, **understanding the building's historical and current functions** and **integrating Renewable Energy Sources (RES) while**

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respecting heritage integrity. Challenges discussed included the high cost of renovations, the complexity of funding mechanisms prioritizing CO2 reduction and limited concrete examples from Latvia. Environmental accessibility and innovative energy solutions were proposed as focus areas for future workshops. Stakeholders emphasised the necessity of tailored financial instruments and sustainable business models for CH building management.

The workshop introduced **social innovation** by addressing environmental accessibility, energy efficiency, and inclusive design in CH buildings, fostering collaboration among local authorities, NGOs, and financial bodies. Although NEB values were not explicitly discussed, the event aligned with these principles by prioritising cultural preservation and accessibility.

RPR's vision of supporting municipalities through knowledge sharing and strategic development was evident throughout the discussions. To enhance future workshops, it was recommended to improve stakeholder engagement through personalised outreach, explicitly integrate NEB values, and include concrete examples of successful projects to inspire municipalities. Expanding the focus to business models and targeted financial mechanisms will further support the sustainable renovation of CH buildings.

3.3.2. Results of the second Social Lab event

The second social Lab workshop took place on 31 October 2024 in Riga, Latvia, focusing on **next-generation solutions for sustainable, inclusive, and resource-efficient CH**. Organised by the RPR, the event brought together key stakeholders to discuss project activities at the AVE SOL building and define future steps for its renovation and energy efficiency improvements. Representatives from local government, energy agencies, and cultural institutions participated in discussions on integrating NEB values, technical aspects of the INHERIT project and establishing a Lab Project to support decision-making in the renovation process.

In the first module, participants applied NEB values - sustainability, aesthetics, and togetherness - to the AVE SOL building's renovation. A pre-module questionnaire revealed a strong awareness of sustainability but less understanding of its application to CH renovations. Stakeholders **explored the integration of renewable energy sources (RES)** like heat pumps and solar photovoltaics while acknowledging the constraints of historic buildings. They emphasised the need for innovative solutions and financial support mechanisms to implement these technologies.

Participants highlighted the importance of inclusiveness, particularly in improving accessibility for people with disabilities. They stressed that solutions should complement the building's historic character. **Public engagement emerged as a priority**, with stakeholders recommending that future design decisions involve active user groups. Discussions on aesthetics focused on preserving the building's architectural integrity while implementing energy-efficient solutions. Participants proposed developing **guidelines to balance modernisation with conservation**. Moving forward,

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they will conduct further technical assessments on heritage-compatible RES technologies, ensure accessibility aligns with cultural values, and enhance public engagement in the redevelopment process.

The second module introduced **technical services and decision-support tools** from the INHERIT project. Stakeholders explored digital solutions, including energy modelling, decision-support tools for renovation planning, and GIS-based systems for sustainable heritage maintenance. They identified real-time energy monitoring and predictive maintenance as key applications for the Latvian pilot project. Participants noted that CH building managers often lack expertise in energy efficiency and **stressed the importance of user-friendly digital tools**. They called for training and dissemination efforts to ensure widespread adoption.

Discussions underscored the **need for a comprehensive database on energy efficiency interventions** in CH buildings to inform policy and funding decisions. Decision-makers expressed interest in using INHERIT's tools to support energy efficiency improvements. The next steps include testing digital tools in the AVE SOL building, organizing training sessions for CH managers, and developing a structured database to guide policy development.

The workshop concluded with the discussion of a **Lab Project** to steer the next phases of the AVE SOL renovation. Stakeholders proposed four potential topics: environmental accessibility, innovative energy efficiency solutions, RES technologies and a full energy audit. Following a vote, they prioritised a detailed energy audit and heating unit inspection for 2025. This assessment will inform the building owner and management's renovation strategy. Next steps include initiating the procurement process for the energy audit, hosting an event to review technical documentation, conducting the audit and presenting findings to stakeholders. Future Lab activities will also address environmental accessibility, innovative energy solutions, and RES technologies. The workshop established a **collaborative framework for advancing energy-efficient renovations in CH buildings**, ensuring that technological innovations align with cultural and historical preservation. Moving forward, efforts will focus on implementing planned assessments, securing funding and refining policy guidelines to promote sustainable heritage renovation practices.

3.4. Gdynia – Poland | FASADA

3.4.1. Results of the Social Labs kick-off event

FASADA's kick-off of the Social Labs event, was organised in June 2024, in synergy with the Gdynia Energy days event. It aimed to propose **renovation measures for residential buildings** that enhance energy efficiency, improve maintenance planning, and increase accessibility for individuals with disabilities, with a specific focus on **social housing**. The pilot building served as a demonstrative

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model, showcasing how CH, sustainability and inclusivity can be integrated to create resilient and adaptable social housing solutions.

The social Lab event attracted 25 participants, including representatives from Gdynia's municipal departments, local authorities, energy providers, construction companies, researchers, building occupants and CH manager. Building occupants focused on **comfort improvements** but expressed concerns about potential rent increases, while stakeholders raised issues about the costs and complexity of implementing innovative technical solutions. One of the conclusions was that CH managers are overloaded with work, causing significant delays. Additionally, there are **no strict regulations** on what interventions are permitted on buildings, leaving much to personal interpretation.

Key insights included the value of organising workshops alongside larger events to increase participation, offering incentives to sustain engagement and prioritizing practical demonstrations of energy efficiency innovations. Future activities will focus on reviewing sensor data from the pilot building to assess energy performance and exploring replicable user scenarios for other historical or social housing buildings. Key activities will also focus on **leveraging AR/VR solutions** to enhance the selection of the optimal renovation scenario for the building owner. FASADA fosters social innovation by promoting collaboration among diverse stakeholders and using technologies like virtual and augmented reality for decision-making. Its emphasis on accessibility, community engagement and digitisation align with the NEB values of sustainability, inclusion and aesthetics. The workshop underscored the importance of **balancing technological advancements with preserving cultural and architectural identity**.

3.4.2. Results of the second Social Lab event

The second social Lab workshop took place in Gdynia in January 2025, Poland, engaging stakeholders from the Gdynia City Hall (incl. CH manager and officer from the Department of Urban Aesthetics) and private construction companies in the INHERIT project (in total 18 participants). Organisers introduced participants to the project's objectives and methodology while exploring its connection to **NEB values** (see Figure 7). Through presentations, interactive sessions, and discussions, participants analysed social, technological, and scientific aspects of the project. The workshop facilitated **a high level of engagement**, focusing on enhancing the well-being of building users, preserving cultural and historical value, and adhering to NEB principles. Discussions led to the selection of a Lab Project, shaping the next steps of the initiative.

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Participants examined key enabling factors for the project's success in the pilot area. They recognised the role of **historical walks, community engagement activities and local decision-makers** in supporting renovations and reducing energy poverty. Economic factors, such as municipal co-financing and lower operational costs, emerged as significant incentives. However, challenges in stakeholder engagement included restrictions in property ownership, financial difficulties and limited community interest.

Figure 7: Stakeholders of FASADA working in the NEB values

Participants proposed **policy adjustments**, such as partial fee exemptions and extended rental agreements under preferential conditions, to encourage resident investment. They also suggested **financial measures** like a municipal 'one-stop shop' for communal services and rent reductions. Education campaigns, advisory services and public consultations were identified as essential tools to build trust and mitigate concerns about rent increases.

The workshop also evaluated the technical aspects of the INHERIT project, particularly its implemented services and assessment pillars. Participants rated '**Preventive maintenance with H-BIM**' as the most useful service, while 'Heritage buildings smartification data exchange' received the lowest rating. Among the assessment pillars, 'Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Costing' ranked highest, indicating strong interest in sustainability and cost efficiency, whereas 'Resilience to Climate and Human-Made Hazards' received the lowest score. Stakeholders explored the broader application of INHERIT services, particularly in preventive maintenance and recognised the benefits of the **H-BIM model for cataloguing repairs** and preserving historic building elements.

Survey results guided discussions on the Lab Project's priorities. Participants identified urban planning improvements around the pilot building as the most critical action, with additional focus on educational programmes, awareness campaigns, and professional design competitions to introduce fresh ideas and attract public attention. They also proposed cultural initiatives, such as guided tours, to increase local awareness of the building's historical and social value.

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The **Lab Project** aims to engage stakeholders in shaping the future of the pilot building and its surroundings. **Participants prioritised urban planning improvements to enhance residents' quality of life and foster community interactions.** They suggested measures such as adding green spaces, installing small architectural elements, and improving public areas to increase the building's attractiveness. To implement the Lab Project, stakeholders recommended collaborative design processes, consultations, and joint selection of functional layouts. They also emphasised the importance of long-term community involvement, encouraging residents to take responsibility for maintaining the revitalised spaces beyond the project's completion.

The workshop concluded with plans to compile findings into a report and share them with stakeholders. The next steps involve conducting an urban analysis, assessing existing land use and greenery, and developing a design strategy that respects historical and spatial considerations. **Engaging local residents throughout all project phases will remain a priority,** ensuring sustainable and community-driven urban improvements. Continued collaboration between stakeholders and the local community will be essential in realising the Lab Project's goals and securing long-term benefits for the pilot area.

3.5. Valladolid – Spain | CARTIF

3.5.1. Results of the Social Labs kick-off event

CARTIF's social Lab kick-off workshop focused on integrating Heritage Building Information Modeling (H-BIM) into the conservation and management of heritage buildings. Using the **World Café method**, the workshop facilitated dialogue on H-BIM's potential for preventive maintenance and its role in engaging diverse stakeholders, particularly citizens, in heritage conservation. The session included presentations on the INHERIT project, H-BIM methodology and collaborative discussions to identify opportunities and challenges in heritage management.

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15 participants from public administration, architecture, engineering, and CH management contributed valuable insights (see Figure 8). Representatives from the Castilla y León Department of Culture shared perspectives on policy and regulation, while architects and engineers offered technical expertise. **Stakeholders, including heritage conservators and building owners, were recognised as integral to conservation efforts, with citizen involvement emphasised as crucial for fostering awareness and responsible use of heritage sites.**

Figure 8: CARTIF stakeholders during the Social Labs kick-off event

Key findings highlighted H-BIM's benefits, including improved decision-making, cost control, and sustainability, but challenges remain. These include the **complexity of applying H-BIM** to geometrically intricate heritage buildings, a lack of communication between HBIM experts and conservators, and the need for standardised solutions. The high learning curve of H-BIM also poses barriers for building owners and smaller organisations unfamiliar with the technology.

The workshop underscored the need for greater stakeholder collaboration and tailored solutions to address specific project needs. **Future Social Labs should focus on making H-BIM more accessible and user-friendly** while fostering training and standardisation to improve interoperability and adoption.

H-BIM represents a key component of **social innovation** within the INHERIT project, promoting transparency, accessibility, and public engagement in heritage conservation. By facilitating collective decision-making and sustainable practices, H-BIM aligns with the **NEB values** of sustainability, togetherness, and aesthetics, supporting CARTIF's vision of using advanced technologies to future-proof heritage conservation.

The workshop achieved its objectives, providing valuable insights into H-BIM's application in heritage conservation. CARTIF's commitment to integrating innovation with sustainability positions it as a leader in advancing inclusive and efficient heritage management practices.

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3.5.2. Results of the second Social Lab event

The **second social Lab workshop** organised by CARTIF took place at the AR-PA TURISMO Fair in Valladolid. The event aimed to raise awareness about **innovative solutions for conserving and renovating CH buildings**, focusing on sustainability, accessibility, and energy efficiency while preserving historical value. Participants, including citizens, technical experts, and CH managers, engaged in discussions on **integrating NEB values into heritage conservation**. **The event showcased INHERIT technologies** such as H-BIM, digital twins, preventive maintenance and AR/VR, providing an opportunity to assess their feasibility and impact. Surveys gathered stakeholder insights on the relevance, viability and risks of these technologies, identifying both opportunities and challenges, including cost concerns and difficulties in adapting new solutions to historic preservation practices.

NEB values were introduced through visual presentations and personalised discussions, emphasising sustainability, inclusivity, and aesthetics. Participants explored enabling factors and challenges related to applying advanced technologies to heritage sites. Barriers included limited understanding of H-BIM, AR, and VR among non-technical participants, high implementation costs, and resistance from stakeholders committed to traditional methods. Proposed solutions involved simplified explanations, case studies, and highlighting long-term cost savings. The post-event survey revealed limited prior knowledge of NEB values among attendees, underscoring the need for continued outreach. **Most participants agreed on the importance of sustainability, accessibility, and maintaining aesthetic integrity**, while some expressed concerns about balancing modern interventions with historical authenticity.

The technical module introduced INHERIT services and assessment pillars through posters and direct discussions. Participants showed strong interest in H-BIM and digital twins for sustainable heritage conservation and recognised the benefits of AR and VR in engaging the public. However, opinions varied on integrating modern materials into historic buildings, with concerns about preserving authenticity. Survey analysis indicated that most participants viewed **heritage buildings as functional spaces**, such as cultural centres or offices. Many prioritised energy efficiency and maintenance cost optimisation, though some questioned whether INHERIT services would significantly improve traditional maintenance methods or reduce costs. Technical stakeholders requested more detailed information to assess the viability and replicability of these solutions.

Survey results guided the ranking of key topics for a **Lab Project**, with sustainability, accessibility, and advanced technologies emerging as top priorities. The most highly rated topics included optimising heritage conservation through H-BIM and digital twins, improving building accessibility, and incorporating green spaces to enhance sustainability. Participants also supported interactive engagement methods, such as guided tours and public workshops, to raise awareness of INHERIT's initiatives. The next steps involve refining project strategies based on survey data, expanding outreach through similar events, and integrating stakeholder feedback into the development of

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INHERIT solutions. Continued engagement with technical and non-technical stakeholders will be crucial to fostering long-term support for the project's objectives.

3.6. Visby – Sweden | UU

3.6.1. Results of the Social Labs kick-off event

The kick-off event, organised by Uppsala University (UU) at the Gotland Campus, brought together 13 participants from diverse stakeholder groups, including tourists and property owners, local authorities, decision-making entities, and the local World Heritage group. **The main objective was to discuss the future of Visby**, particularly its transformation into a sustainable, livable city while preserving its medieval heritage. The event aimed to **foster collaboration** among stakeholders and raise awareness of the environmental and social impacts of activities on the city's built environment, with a focus on the strategic development of Visby as a World Heritage site.

Stakeholder participation was key, with **diverse perspectives contributing to the discussions**. Property owners, given the city's historical significance and local authorities, responsible for balancing conservation and urban development, played vital roles. The local World Heritage group's involvement highlighted the intersection of heritage conservation and sustainability. Despite the broad interest in maintaining Visby as a living city, there was a lack of discussions around the NEB values of sustainability, inclusion and aesthetics, revealing an area for improvement in aligning future workshops with broader European initiatives.

Key findings included a strong local interest in preserving **Visby as a vibrant urban space** and stakeholders stressed the need for clear, locally relevant actions. Insights from the workshop highlighted the **need for further refinement of methodologies**, particularly when dealing with historic buildings. Stakeholders expressed interest in future activities but called for the involvement of technical experts to address the complexities of energy measurement, sensor placement, and sustainability. The project's focus on local engagement remains critical, with an emphasis on tailoring tools to the unique characteristics of Visby.

The project embodies **social innovation** by fostering collaborative efforts between stakeholders **to balance heritage preservation with modern environmental needs**. By promoting inclusive community engagement, it targets residents, tourists and businesses to contribute to sustainability solutions, ensuring both affordability and accessibility in Visby's old town.

Although the NEB values were not explicitly discussed, the event aligned with UU's vision of raising awareness about the impacts of activities on the built environment. To better align with European priorities, it is recommended that future activities explicitly incorporate the NEB values of

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sustainability, inclusion and aesthetics. Additionally, **the involvement of technical experts** and a focus on concrete, locally relevant actions **will be crucial** to advancing the project's goals.

3.6.2. Results of the second Social Lab event

The INHERIT Social Lab Workshop at Campus Gotland **focused on the NEB initiative and its relevance to Visby's World Heritage site**. The Lab started with the NEB National Contact Point presenting the job done and the good practices at national level, to continue with a table discussion where heritage aspects have been linked to a sustainable development of the historic building stock in Visby, exploring how CH can contribute to its sustainable urban development. The workshop revealed limited engagement from local stakeholders, particularly residents and business owners, with no participation from tourism organisations. Participants highlighted the **need for greater awareness and local buy-in for sustainability solutions** that align with Visby's historic environment. The discussions emphasised the importance of traditional building knowledge in the long-term management of Visby's built environment. Social and cultural values were recognised as key factors in sustainable urban planning, with diversity in building functions promoting inclusivity. Participants stressed the role of greenery in urban settings and the need for public investment in infrastructure to support year-round use. The workshop also explored ways to integrate sustainability solutions with cultural values.

Suggestions included **adapting traditional materials and techniques for modern construction, increasing education in heritage conservation, and implementing regulatory changes to counter over-commercialisation**. Public-private collaboration was seen as essential for sustainable urban development. Participants also proposed a more holistic approach to integrating Visby's World Heritage status into the broader city strategy. The workshop helped address this gap by fostering discussions on how NEB values could shape Visby's future development. However, it is not excluded that NEB values will be further explored in relation to a sustainable development of the buildings and the building stock in Visby.

3.7. Izmir – Türkiye | IBB

3.7.1. Results of the Social Labs kick-off event

The Social Lab kick-off event, organised by the Izmir Metropolitan Municipality (IBB), gathered 21 participants, including stakeholders from energy performance, CH, and sustainability sectors. The workshop aimed to explore **sustainable and energy-efficient solutions for the pilot building**, which serves various users, and to create a holistic model combining heritage preservation, renewable energy adoption, and community engagement. The long-term goal was to **foster social inclusion and establish a sustainable exploitation model** for the building. However, key discussions on the

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integration of NEB values, such as sustainability, inclusion, and aesthetics, were absent, revealing a gap in understanding these principles within the project.

The event attracted a **diverse group of stakeholders**, including academics, residents, engineers, and conservationists, who provided valuable insights into both technical and cultural aspects of the building's sustainability. However, the absence of private-sector representatives and additional CH experts limited the depth of technical discussions, especially regarding energy measurement and sensor placement. Participants identified **several challenges**, such as the lack of familiarity with NEB values and barriers to involving private-sector partners due to IBB's need to remain impartial.

Feedback indicated **strong interest in future events**, with participants suggesting the inclusion of energy measurement and sensor placement experts to address these technical gaps. There was also a call for more structured meetings with focused agendas and clear goals to enhance the quality of discussions and decision-making. **The workshop reinforced the value of social innovation** by bringing together multiple stakeholder perspectives, promoting collective decision-making and ensuring solutions are socially beneficial, sustainable and supported by the community.

While IBB's vision aligns with NEB values in terms of social inclusion and sustainability, these values were not adequately addressed during the workshop. It was recommended that future activities incorporate them more explicitly by providing training or workshops to educate participants.

3.7.2. Results of the second Social Lab event

The second social Lab workshop took place on 29 January 2025 at the Ahmet Piriştina City Archive and Museum (APIKAM) in İzmir, organised by the İzmir Metropolitan Municipality. The event focused on understanding **NEB values, integrating technical services** and discussing the sustainability, accessibility, and energy efficiency of the pilot building while preserving its historical value. It aimed to **expand the stakeholder group** by involving experts who could contribute technical knowledge and influence future decisions. The format included presentations, discussions and interactive sessions such as the NEB flower poster activity and surveys to generate ideas for the Lab Project. Academic consultants suggested involving PhD students to further analyse the implementation of advanced technologies like H-BIM, digital twins and AR/VR in the pilot building. The opening session featured speeches from key figures in historic conservation and architecture, followed by an introduction to the INHERIT project. Presentations on NEB values included international and national case studies, alongside an interactive exercise where stakeholders identified the most relevant NEB values for the pilot building. The technical aspects of the project were also discussed, with participants engaging in Q&A sessions using digital tools such as Mentimeter.

Participants explored NEB values in relation to the pilot building, visually identifying and prioritising the most relevant aspects through the NEB flower poster activity. Discussions

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emphasised integrating renewable energy sources such as solar, wind and geothermal while maintaining the historical and architectural integrity of the building. Stakeholders identified **barriers** such as financial constraints, regulatory challenges and difficulties in adapting new technologies to historic structures. The need for inclusive approaches that address both policymakers and the local community emerged as a key theme. **Potential solutions** included policy adjustments, awareness campaigns, and financial incentives to support conservation efforts.

The technical module introduced participants to INHERIT services and assessment pillars relevant to the pilot building. Discussions focused on determining the most critical factors for conservation and adaptation, particularly the role of **smart technologies in heritage management**. Participants evaluated which INHERIT services could provide the most value and considered how project assessment tools could enhance decision-making. They explored the potential of displaying real-time energy usage data in the INHERIT evaluation interface to improve stakeholder engagement. Insights from the Mentimeter questionnaire further shaped discussions on assessment priorities and technical solutions.

A collaborative survey conducted before and during the workshop helped identify key topics for the **Lab Project**. The highest-voted topics included projects with a cultural message, interaction with local initiatives, engagement with APIKAM visitors, school participation and contributions to sustainable tourism. Stakeholders proposed forming a working group to conduct presentations and **organise a joint workshop with students**, alongside a co-working event aligned with the building's academic and research functions. They also suggested **using the courtyard for interactive activities**, such as lighting the tower based on real-time energy usage data. As the next step, stakeholders agreed to organise a workshop in the APIKAM courtyard, focusing on historic buildings in İzmir, energy efficiency and integrating new technologies in CH conservation. The project will incorporate surveys to enhance engagement and inclusiveness, ensuring alignment with INHERIT's broader goals and promoting sustainable heritage management.

4. The first feedback loop in the Social Life Cycle Analysis (S-LCA)

The Social Life Cycle Analysis - further also Social Life Cycle Assessment or SLCA - is a specific means of the INHERIT project to collect data about the level of social inclusiveness, economic efficiency and environmental responsibility at each pilot site. To better grasp the different meanings of these specific terms, ZSI proposed an **overarching definition of the term 'social responsibility'**, which addresses all three dimensions. This proposed definition will be discussed later in this chapter.

The data collected for the S-LCA is both of quantitative (through a survey) and qualitative (through in-depth expert interviews) in nature. Data collection happens **at three stages** of the project, according to the GA: At the beginning - this stage has already been completed, and the first results are presented in this chapter – midway, and towards the project end. Based on the data collected, a related assessment of the three mentioned levels for each of the INHERIT pilots is done. By the end of the project, it will be possible to compare the levels over time, indicating potential improvements or declines in inclusiveness, efficiency, and responsibility. **Collected results and the comparative assessment of all seven pilots will be published in D2.4: Report on social impact & spillover effects of INHERIT, fostering NEB values & principles**, due towards the end of the project.

ZSI, given its status as a social sciences research institute, focuses its analysis on the inclusiveness level while all three levels retain their relevance vis-à-vis the broader project objectives. The overall goal is to put forward concrete recommendations on how the involvement of various actors in the governance of each pilot building or site can be improved, drawing on the collective data from the assessment phases. **In this light, the S-LCA works in synergy with two other activities of the project: the Social Lab series and the technical solutions development**, and connect with that, the monitoring of how solutions perform in the pilot sites. The Social Labs are the primary activity of the pilots to open themselves towards both specific stakeholders and the general society.

Social Labs are a concrete offering to take part in a co-creation inspired process to jointly build ideas and/or visions for the future (use) of each pilot building, facilitated by a structured process - four Social Labs in total over the full project runtime - and supervised by a core team of the INHERIT project. As we could observe in **the first S-LCA assessment, some of the experts taking part in the interviews were also participants in the Social Lab processes** of the individual pilots. **This correlation has reciprocal effects**: Social Labs support pilots in their 'opening' process towards society, potentially improving inclusiveness, accessibility, and participatory activities in the medium and long-term. This, on the other hand, is likely to be reflected in the responses made by interviewees of the S-LCA process. Regarding the development and monitoring of solutions, it is

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likely to expect that the continuous testing of technical solutions for each pilot site, supervised by INHERIT partners and in close collaboration with the users of as well as stakeholders to the building, also triggers a personal reflection process about the dimensions pertaining to the S-LCA. Most of the technical solutions developed within INHERIT target either the economic efficiency and/or environmental responsibility performance of the building, while some are also promising in terms of strengthening social inclusiveness. Upon completing the demonstration of technical solutions towards the project end, we expect respondents in the final S-LCA interview round directly referring to some of the effects created by the solution implemented at the pilot they are attached to. As a last synergy to other INHERIT activities, **the S-LCA findings overall, once available after the final assessment, will feed into the decision support services built in WP4 and the policy guidance documents prepared in WP6.** Adding up to all other synergies as described, the transfer of key findings from the S-LCA into these two key outputs of the INHERIT project, where applicable, can make the S-LCA an even more impactful task in the framework of the whole INHERIT project.

With a view on the methodology applied in the S-LCA, the interviews and the survey were already briefly mentioned. The background research to better define the scope of the assessment was done at the beginning of 2024. At the same time, a working definition for social responsibility, proposed by ZSI and adopted by the INHERIT partners, was introduced. **The working definition of social responsibility** addresses the three levels of the S-LCA assessment and is embedded in the core literature examined for this activity:

Social responsibility addresses the organisational governance and management procedures effectively carried out by owners, operators and decision-makers in the daily operation of their CH building or site. It relates to the triple bottom line of measuring the operational management of an organisation (building), including economic efficiency, environmental responsibility and social inclusiveness (INHERIT working definition of social responsibility).

Let's take a closer look at the literature studied (including ISO standards), the indicators for the assessment chosen, and the interview guideline. The indicators chosen for the S-LCA stem from **two key sources**: First, **the ISO standards on environmental management (ISO 14040) and social responsibility (ISO 26000)**; and second, **the literature (academic, policy, and technical) on energy, operation/governance, and cooperation with the third sector.** When searching and selecting literature, we carefully checked every content as to the relevance for social responsibility and social inclusion. After having completed the first step of literature screening and background research, a pool of potentially suitable indicators was built. This larger set of indicators was divided into three topics, namely:

- energy and social inclusivity;
- CH management/operation and social inclusivity;

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- third sector and social inclusivity.

Within these **smaller pools of topics**, indicators were further classified with information such as framework (they are part of), objective (they are pursuing), and identifier (to provide a clear source allowing their unique identification), as per Table 1. The picture below (see Figure 9), visualises the approach selected for developing suitable indicators for the S-LCA.

The full list consists of 16 indicators is available to ZSI. All indicators will be discussed then in more detail in the already mentioned final deliverable on the S-LCA (see D2.4). The study fields ‘energy and social responsibility’ and ‘CH management and social responsibility’ consist of five indicators each. The study field ‘third sector cooperation and social responsibility’ consists of four indicators and the so called ‘complementary fields’, which are basically representing two other core frameworks of the INHERIT project (on the one hand the four technical services from WP4, and on the other the NEB values derived from the NEB framework) consists of two more indicators. **In total, this sums up to 16 indicators representing the intersection of the dominant frameworks that shape the social lifecycle analysis of the INHERIT project**, as can be also seen from the graphic presented below (see Figure 10).

Figure 9: Visualisation of the S-LCA approach

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Figure 10: S-LCA frameworks and indicators

In the following Tables (see Table 1, 2, 3, and 4), **two example indicators for each of the study fields of the S-LCA are presented**. As metadata to each indicator entry, the indicator’s source (framework), objective, content (subject), and identifier (unique reference) are provided. Drawing on the full list of 16 indicators with related metadata, the INHERIT S-LCA questionnaire was developed in April 2024 and shared with pilot partners for the 1st assessment phase thereafter.

Table 1: Energy and social inclusivity, responsibility

Framework (external or INHERIT)	Objective	Core subject	Indicator	Identifier (ISO, Standard etc.)
EN 16883:2017 Conservation of cultural heritage - guidelines for improving the energy performance of historic buildings	Improving the energy performance of historic buildings	Better energy performance	Lower CO2 emission; higher production rate of own electricity; less electricity consumption	EN 16883:2017

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Planning energy retrofits of historic buildings (EN16883:2017 in practice)	Retrofit of CH buildings	Socially accepted retrofit concepts	Use rate of renewable energy sources; total direct or indirect greenhouse gas emissions; percentage of reusable/recycled material used in retrofitting	DOI: 10.18777
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Table 2: CH management and social inclusivity, responsibility

Framework (external or INHERIT)	Objective	Core subject	Indicator	Identifier (ISO, Standard etc.)
Social Life Cycle Management in CH sector (no standard published yet, work in progress)	Social innovation in CH management	Triple bottom line for good governance: social inclusivity, economic efficiency and environmental sustainability	S-LCA principles incorporated in governance and management procedures of the building	INHERIT S-LCA presentation
Competence framework for CH management (UNESCO); Guidebook on standards for drafting CH management plans (OSCE)	Adaptive reuse or valorisation of CH	Defining new roles for CH valuable for society	Reskilling and upskilling of CH management personnel (owners, operators) with CH management competences	ISBN: 978-92-9223-688-5 (UNESCO); https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/2/d/461188.pdf (OSCE)

Table 3: Third sector and social inclusivity, responsibility

Framework (external or INHERIT)	Objective	Core subject	Indicator	Identifier (ISO, Standard etc.)
ICOMOS International Charter for Cultural Heritage Tourism; ISO 21902 - Tourism and related services (accessible tourism for all)	Cultural tourism	Responsible and sustainable tourism management for CH	Level of protection of CH and of community rights vis-a-vis tourism and alignment of CH tourism management with UN SDGs	ISO 21902:2021 (Tourism and related services); ICOMOS International CH Tourism Charter 2022

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UNESCO Culture for Development Indicators: Heritage sustainability	Mobilisation of public and private support (financial and/or PR etc.) to support the role of CH as an important societal value for the future	Involvement of the private and public sector	Financial or non-financial support provided by actors; integration of all society members in developing CH sustainability goals	UNESCO Culture for Development Indicators https://www.unesco.org/cr/eativity/en/activities/cdis
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Table 4: Complementary fields

Framework (external or INHERIT)	Objective	Core subject	Indicator	Identifier (ISO, Standard etc.)
INHERIT WP4: The four technical services	Reflective technology development which integrates societal dimensions	Which social impact (positive, negative) will the four technical services have?	Technology progress covering fields such as environment	INHERIT WP4 Technical service descriptions
NEB Framework	NEB values as a new aesthetic approach to combine design and functionality of CH	Working with NEB values in CH renovation	Integration of NEB values and working principles and relevant ambitions related to beauty, inclusion and sustainability	NEB Compass

4.1. The Interview questionnaire: structure and learnings from the 1st assessment

Based on what has been written above, the questionnaire for the 1st assessment consisted of the following chapters.

1. Introduction;
2. Energy and social responsibility in CH;
3. Social responsibility in CH management and operation;

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4. Social responsibility in CH through cooperation with the third sector, including the private sector;
5. Best practices;
6. NEB values in CH.

Now that the 1st assessment phase has been concluded and a knowledge sharing workshop has been organised providing space for joint reflection, the feedback deriving from the discussions with pilot partners is the starting point for preparing the second S-LCA assessment. **The knowledge sharing workshop took place on June 4, 2024, hosted by ZSI with participation of all pilot partners.**

During this workshop, pilot partners were explicitly invited to share their feedback about the interview process with the owners, operators and decision-makers of their pilot building. Apart from specific individual feedback, which was received from pilot partners during this workshop, one point of feedback was shared by all pilot partners equally. It concerns the fact that several experts found it difficult to answer all questions from all fields, arguing that they have expertise in one field specifically but not in all (for instance, an energy expert is not necessarily an expert on CCH management at the same time). Therefore, **while the design of questions and the thematic scope of the interview template was very much appreciated in general, pilot partners wish to have a more tailored set of questions, which is adapted to the actual local context, including local stakeholders, for the next assessment coming up.** This could remedy the problem of specific questions left unanswered (or answered with 'N/A') in future assessments.

The most important milestones (see Figure 11) reached for the S-LCA at the time of writing this deliverable are:

- Hosting of an **internal preparatory workshop** (online) on 21.02.2024 to discuss the role of pilots in the S-LCA process (train-the-trainers) and to align the cooperation with other WPs concerned;
- Preparation of **interview guidelines for 1st assessment**, based on desk research, indicator collection and final selection (main sources: ISO 14040, ISO 26000, and academic, policy, technical standards literature);
- **Analysis of responses** collected during the first assessment from June- July 2024;
- Hosting of a **knowledge-sharing workshop** on 04.06.2024 to facilitate the exchange of experiences between pilots about a) contacting experts for interviews and b) suitability of questions for the target group;
- **Presentation of interim analysis** from 1st assessment during the INHERIT in-person meeting in Valladolid, Nov. 20. 2024.

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Figure 11: S-LCA milestones

We conclude this section with a short outlook: **due to an iterative analysis** on the co-creation activities of the Social Labs and the series of S-LCA assessments that are influenced by it (see the synergy of activities as earlier described in this chapter), **it is foreseen to adjust the design and the implementation mode of the SLC-A for forthcoming assessments**. As has become evident from the results of the first assessment phase – shown below for each of the pilot partners which have taken part in this assessment - experts had difficulties (some more, some less) to comprehensively answering all questions of all three thematic blocs of the questionnaire. To gain more robust and more complete feedback in future editions, it is an option to interview different experts from different fields, **while experts only addressing those questions pertaining to their expertise** (for instance, energy manager answers the questions from the energy chapter, tourism expert answers the questions from the third sector cooperation chapter, etc.) This may become a more appropriate approach to allow for comparability between answers, which are then in-depth and comprehensive, provided over time. In this context, it is under further consideration to include another focused assessment cycle to better address stakeholders according to their expertise and to align and focus indicators based on a jointly agreed denominator approach. To align with the characteristics and needs per pilot, echoing one of the main feedback points from several pilots, **one additional question could be included in the questionnaire helping to assess change through the co-creation and technology testing**. In doing so, comparability and specification is expected to be established.

4.2. Interim results of the Social Life Cycle Analysis

As a first step, respondents from pilot areas were asked to **self-assess their knowledge** of social responsibility in CH management, using the Likert scale ranging from 1 ‘no knowledge at all’ to 7 ‘very deep knowledge’. Their responses are presented in Table 5 below:

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Table 5: Pilots' self-assessment

	Participants	Self-assessed knowledge on social responsibility in CH management (1: no knowledge – 7: very deep knowledge)
REGEA, pilot in Jastrebarsko, Croatia	Leader of the section for general affairs and public relations, City of Jastrebarsko	2
	Deputy Mayor, City of Jastrebarsko	5
	Head of Department for Economy and EU funds, City of Jastrebarsko	6
	Advisor in Department for Economy and EU funds, City of Jastrebarsko	2
ELLET, pilot in Athens, Greece	Lawyer, ex-president of the Greek National Tourism Organisation, expert in creating cultural experience for tourists	6
	Professor at the NTUA programme “protection of monuments”	5
	Architect-restorer, member of the NEB committee in Greece	6
RPR, pilot in Riga, Latvia	Architect, resident of the neighbourhood Plaka near the pilot building	7
	Managing director of Ekodoma	6
	Energy manager	4
	Energy manager	3
FASADA, pilot in Gdynia, Poland	Director of Renesco	5
	Senior inspector at the energy department of Gdynia city hall	3

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CARTIF, pilot in Valladolid, Spain	Energy manager in the municipality (Head of energy department)	2
	Architect in the buildings department of Gdynia city hall	5
	Owner and manager of demo building, Head of property administration, ZBILK (management of municipal buildings and premises)	1
	Head of negotiations department, Directorate General for CH	4
	Architect, Directorate General for CH	3
	Architect	4
	Technician	4
UU, pilot in Visby, Sweden	Property Manager in the church of Sweden	4
	World Heritage coordinator in town of Visby	6
	Operational developer	4
	CH advisor and site manager	4
IBB, pilot in Izmir, Türkiye	Responsible for international projects at Izmir Municipality, City Archive and Museum	4
	Mechanical Engineer	4
	Electrical Engineer	2
	Architect in CH	5
	Restoration Specialist, Project Chief	6

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After the self-assessment, the respondents answered several questions relating to the **three main topics** identified for the first S-LCA assessment and presented above in this chapter. Namely:

- **Energy and social responsibility in CH** (see Table 6);
- **Social responsibility in CH management** (see Table 7);
- **Cooperation with the third sector** (see Table 8).

The following table provides answers that offer insights into their knowledge and ideas regarding these important questions for CH management.

Table 6: Assessment on Energy and social responsibility in cultural heritage

	Energy and social responsibility in CH
Jastrebarsko – Croatia REGEA	The building has rather bad energy performance at the moment. A strong wish to introduce renewable energy sources and energy consumption optimisation measures was expressed. An energy retrofit in the past gave details about which specific measures are needed for the building.
Athens – Greece ELLET	The building currently has a medium-level performance when it comes to energy efficiency. The overall objective should be to improve the energy performance without compromising the specific character of the building and its surrounding area; Moreover, the community should be involved in the process. High costs and strict regulations make technical interventions in the building complicated, i.e. solar roof tiles are not allowed as they would alter the morphology of the building.
Riga – Latvia RPR	The building currently has rather bad energy performance. We need to replace the heating system and prevent cold air from infiltration into the building by renovation of windows and doors; doors and windows are a low-price solution; thus, it makes great sense to start with these adaptations; building should undergo a complete renovation. In view of the concert hall, the acoustics, seating arrangements and technical capabilities must be improved - renovation should focus on optimizing the space both for performers and the audience. No retrofit is planned - immediate improvements would concern the lighting and the heating system.
Gdynia – Poland FASADA	Respondents, overall, estimated the building's current energy performance as very bad (3-1-1-1). Asked about what should be improved in that regard, different suggestions were made. Energy efficiency measures could be implemented and investments in renewable energy sources could be made. Moreover, the establishment of energy assistance programs and further education on efficient energy use for building occupants was suggested.

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Valladolid – Spain CARTIF	<p>Respondents, overall, estimated the building’s current energy performance as quite good (4-4-4-2). In view of what could be improved in this regard, the following suggestions were made: zoning of air conditioning, cooling installations, use of automatic shading devices to avoid sun exposure in common areas, automation of installations, replacement of windows with newer ones, solar control. Another person said that the installation of solar panels in the parking lot could provide energy for buildings and electric cars.</p>
Visby – Sweden UU	<p>For the Visby pilot building, only one from the four experts gave an answer to the question about ranking the energy efficiency of the pilot (answer was 4). At this point it is important to repeat again (as has been mentioned earlier in this deliverable already) that Visby is the only pilot of INHERIT where more than one building is included in the research activities of the project. In fact, in Visby we deal with the whole historic city centre. We assume that this is also the reason why experts had difficulties with the present question (in fact this was supported by one respondent mentioning that ‘a ranking would depend on the building, but in Visby we are dealing with the whole city centre’). In view of the forthcoming assessments, we took note of this as a learning and will consider a more tailor-made approach. Another expert said that common solutions need to be found for all buildings in the city centre.</p>
Izmir – Türkiye IBB	<p>Experts assessed the energy performance of the building in Izmir with 3-2-1-3-3, indicating a rather bad performance at the moment. The five experts also provided a few more details about what they mean: For instance, heating and cooling need significant improvement, while the reduction of energy consumption is another important aspect to improve energy performance overall.</p>

Regarding the assessment of social responsibility in CH management, participants had to assess how deep the principles of social inclusivity, economic efficiency and environmental sustainability are embedded in the buildings’ daily operation procedures on a scale from 1 to 7 (1: only partially – 7: all principles are reflected and operationalised). Further, we asked on which level citizens participate in the management of the building, based on the 7-stepped ladder of citizen participation in CH management from the Organisation for World Heritage Cities, divided into three groups of stakeholders (citizens, policy makers and private representatives).

Table 7: Assessment on Social responsibility in CH management

Social responsibility in CH management	
Jastrebarsko – Croatia REGEA	<p>This resulted in the following rating: 2-2-2-2. Different ideas for re-use or valorisation of the building were shared, such as a mixed-use complex for</p>

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	<p>residential and commercial purposes and as a public space; adding a museum or library; changing it into a building for cultural purposes. Taking all answers together, respondents consider policymakers as the closest involved in the management/operation.</p>
<p>Athens – Greece ELLET</p>	<p>This resulted in the following rating: 3-4-4-6. The current use of the building would already support community groups; As an idea for valorisation, the historical features should be preserved while creating a heritage museum with an educational function for the public at the same time; Regarding the level of citizen engagement on the 7-steps ladder, respondents ranked citizens (out of policy makers, citizens and private representatives) highest on average (4-1-2-5).</p>
<p>Riga – Latvia RPR</p>	<p>This resulted in the following rating: 5-1-1-4; The building is already used for the needs of various community needs as choir groups; However, if the building had modern convertible chairs and light equipment, then it would be possible to rent the building for other purposes and obtain additional economic benefits. Regarding the assessment of citizens’ involvement in the management/operation of the building, respondents ranked all three stakeholder groups (citizens, policy makers and private representatives) as rather passively involved on average.</p>
<p>Gdynia – Poland FASADA</p>	<p>This resulted in the following rating: 3-2-2. One of the respondents didn’t make a rating, stating that he/she is not aware of ISO 26000 on social responsibility and that this is not implemented in his/her organisation. Regarding ideas for valorisation of the building, suggestions such as the establishment of educational programs, guided tours, and interactive exhibitions to promote cultural understanding and foster appreciation for CH, and to generate revenue to support the building’s preservation and operation were made; Others mentioned cultural function, shops, offices and the development of green areas surrounding the building. Compared to other pilots, valorisation ideas concerning the structure of the building were mentioned more often (cleaning and painting of façade, renewal of windows, replacement of staircase doors, removal of ‘canopy’ on balcony last floor, renovation of staircase, identical entrance doors to all units etc.). Regarding the assessment of citizens’ involvement in the management/operation of the building, respondents ranked all three stakeholder groups (citizens, policy makers and private representatives) as quite involved. Citizens are involved for consultation, education, promotion and grassroots-led negotiations, policymakers are involved for consultations (2x), grassroot-led negotiations and self-management and private representatives are involved for consultation, protection, advisory and self-management.</p>
<p>Valladolid – Spain CARTIF</p>	<p>This resulted in the following rating: 6-3-4-4. These results suggest that the principles are acknowledged and partially adopted already, but there is room for</p>

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	<p>improvement. Asked about valorisation ideas, one respondent said clearly that he/she doesn't see any need for adaptive reuse or valorisation of the property; Another person answered in the same direction ('not applicable for the building'), whereas one expert brought up the interesting idea of opening a school for trades related to conservation and rehabilitation and a school for the arts (dance, music, painting etc.). Regarding the assessment of citizens' involvement in the management/operation of the building, respondents ranked citizens and policymakers as quite involved, while private representatives were mentioned by two respondents as a stakeholder group 'not applicable' for this question. As examples, citizens are involved for education/promotion (2x), policymakers are involved for partnership and protection, and private representatives are involved for education/promotion.</p>
Visby – Sweden UU	<p>This resulted in the following rating: 3-2-2, while one expert answered with 'N/A' (no answer). Asked about valorisation ideas, one expert raised the point of affordable housing and suggested that the city should buy a new stock of housing which should become available for renting to underrepresented groups. Another expert thought of the Visby city centre as a 'place for hybrid functionality, depending on the season (weather)', without becoming more precise. And yet another answer was pointing to the fact that solar panels would be a very good starting point for moving the energy supply sources of the city from non-renewable to renewable sources, if the local policy framework for the protection and conservation of the city centre's buildings would allow for that. Currently though, the policy of the city government does not allow the installation of solar panels. Regarding the assessment of citizens' involvement in the management/operation of the building, respondents gave the following estimations: Citizens: self-management/consultation/partnership/advisory (they are pretty engaged in thoughts and opinions); Policymakers: both high and low/grassroot-led negotiation/advisory/grassroot-led negotiation; Private representatives: N/A/grassroot-led negotiation/self-management/partnership.</p>
Izmir – Türkiye IBB	<p>This resulted in the following rating: 3-3-1-1-5. When it comes to valorization, there was a strong preference visible towards opening the building more to cultural, leisure time and professional use. The idea of using the building as an art gallery or cultural center was mentioned from one expert, while another said that a library and co-working space would be his/her solution for the future; Another expert preferred to open the building for social projects and the community. Regarding the assessment of citizens' involvement in the management/operation of the building, respondents gave the following estimations: Citizens: 4/1/1/1/1; Policy Makers: 4/2/2/4/N/A; Private Representatives: 4/4/4/3/N/A.</p>

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Table 8 Assessment on Cooperation with the Third Sector

	Cooperation with the third sector
Jastrebarsko – Croatia REGEA	While the only current purpose of the building is of governmental nature, respondents addressed the idea to open it more for creative or cultural purposes; The INHERIT project was mentioned here as a positive example how this change could be initiated.
Athens – Greece ELLET	ELLET promotes the idea of sustainable tourism and accepts financial support by private actors; Financial support is needed as antiquities are found in the building's basement that need preservation for the future; ELLET has partnerships with third sector actors but could need more; Additionally, partnering with cultural and creative industries can enhance the building's value and engage the community in innovative ways.
Riga – Latvia RPR	Asked whether the respondents have ever considered to a) integrate and promote the building in the larger context of responsible and sustainable tourism, b) mobilize financial (or non-financial) support by private and public actors to promote the building's importance for future generations or c) seek partnerships with other actors from cultural and creative industries, the majority of answers was 'yes' (11 out of 12 answers).
Gdynia – Poland FASADA	Asked whether the respondents have ever considered to a) integrate and promote the building in the larger context of responsible and sustainable tourism, b) mobilise financial (or non-financial) support by private and public actors to promote the building's importance for future generations or c) seek partnerships with other actors from cultural and creative industries, the majority of answers was 'no' (10 out of 12). This is quite exceptional compared to all other pilots, where some or most of the specific cooperation ideas with the third sector were in fact considered by the experts.
Valladolid – Spain CARTIF	For the CARTIF pilot building it became quickly evident that the experts don't favour the idea of cooperation with the third sector. One expert gave an exemplary answer and mentioned that none of the potential cooperation ideas with the third sector is interesting for the pilot, both because the building is not focused on tourism and because it is in an adequate operation condition with sufficient financial investments to safeguard historical conservation. In our interpretation this is a signal that currently no change is needed and also not wanted. The answer of another expert goes in the opposite direction though: There is a possibility to open the building to the community through visits and cultural events, supported by associations and foundations. Another expert mentioned that the owners and operators of the building should raise awareness

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	among different associations and neighbours that the building is a ‘common good’, as this could help to create a sense of belonging and attachment, becoming visible through supporting its mission and sharing its values.
Visby – Sweden UU	Overall, experts of the Visby pilot were very positive and knowledgeable about cooperation with the third sector. A particular project was mentioned in that regard, which had been already implemented in the past. It was called ‘The trip to a sustainable Hansestad’ and dealt with location usage and how sustainable tourism could be used to develop a place. At the same time experts pointed to the limitations that come by being a member of specific networks, such as the association for world heritage, to which the city of Visby belongs. This association, in the word of the expert, is a forum for discussions, yet it does not provide the framework to open our city for cooperation with the third sector.
Izmir – Türkiye IBB	Integrating the pilot building in the broader context of responsible and sustainable cultural tourism is essential, as expressed by one expert; The organisation of efficient exhibition and seminar programs and of international events will contribute to developing the third sector cooperation, as the city of Izmir is already an attraction point for foreign tourists, added another expert. Hosting international art exhibitions/events could lead to partnerships for promoting cultural collaboration. It was also emphasized that cooperation with the third sector is a crucial point, as it allows us to preserve the building for future generations. This would also foster a sense of ownership and pride among residents and stakeholders.

To conclude the interview, respondents were invited to share any best practices related to social inclusion in CH buildings that they were aware of. **Additionally, they were asked to rate the importance of the NEB values**, according to their perception. The responses are presented below in Table 9 and 10.

Table 9: Best practices of social inclusion from other CH buildings

	Best practices
Jastrebarsko – Croatia REGEA	Revitalisation of Rijeka's industrial zone; particularly important was the extensive involvement of societal groups in the revitalisation process.
Athens – Greece ELLET	There are many good practices for CH and tourism sustainability, in particular on Greek islands; Cyclades were historically based in the agro-economic sector. Traditional rural houses were preserved and utilised for agrotourism. In the example of traditional rural houses, various residents are managing the business

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	<p>as they all work together in the building. Therefore, all the decisions are participatory, and the level of inclusion is high. It is a very specific case though and I cannot think of how this could be repeated by the pilot. Ellet has a high number of volunteers that maybe can be involved more in decision making.</p>
Rīga – Latvia RPR	<p>In my opinion, the Kalnciema quarter serves as a good example, as they organize a variety of events such as seminars, educational programs, and discussions. Given the good location of our building, it would be possible to adopt some of their methods as well; The art space MALA is a good example from Cēsis. They organize various types of events, including young people's as well; While the answer above shows some of the respondents are aware of other best practices, another respondent mentioned he does not know of any best practices.</p>
Gdynia – Poland FASADA	<p>The following examples of best practices were mentioned: City of Gdańsk, where the Brownfield Energetyków Street was changed into a cultural place where people can meet, eat (foodhall) and listen to concerts, music; Fort Grodzisko in Gdańsk. Where the former fortification was converted into the Hevelianum Science Centre. The science centre hosts temporary exhibitions and events for the local community, e.g. commemorating historical occasions. The Hevelianum is a place accessible to people with physical, sight, hearing and intellectual disabilities, as well as those with the autism spectrum. One respondent mentioned that the different functions from the pilot building of FASADA would significantly limit the possibility of replicating the approach from the Hevelianum Science Centre.</p>
Valladolid – Spain CARTIF	<p>Two examples were mentioned in view of best practices. Once, the REACH repository, as a database for CH buildings and innovative use, and second the town of Birr in Ireland, where an old church is used as a public library.</p>
Visby – Sweden UU	<p>For best practices, experts mainly focused on examples in regional proximity, concluding that there aren't many good examples of this here in Gotland. The earlier mentioned past project about the sustainable Hansestadt, in which Visby took part, was brought up here again as a good practice example; Another expert said that he would like to have multiple cultural/societal exchange programs and integration projects with younger people in particular.</p>
Izmir – Türkiye IBB	<p>According to the five experts, the city of Izmir boasts several best practice examples: restoration of Ahmet Ağa mansion; reuse and restoration of a house In Buca Kasaplar square Izmir Tarih Design Atelier; the historical four factory restoration, Konak Kemeraltı (historical city center) Lighting Masterplan & Havra and 848 Street, etc.</p>

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Table 10: Rating the importance of the NEB values sustainability, aesthetics, inclusion

	NEB values rating
Jastrebarsko – Croatia REGEA	All 3 principles are equally important; aesthetics is very important because of the building's location in the very city centre; inclusivity and sustainability are most important; sustainability is the most important.
Athens – Greece ELLET	All 3 values are important. The future vision for the building is to enhance sustainability, to preserve the existing level of aesthetics, which is very high, and to expand accessibility to new groups of society, that have not visited or used it up to now; Sustainability can be achieved with energy optimization, aesthetic shall be preserved by maintaining its antiquities and identity of the building. Inclusion can better be achieved if we find a way for the building to be accessible for disabled people as currently it is not, due to the arrangement of spaces to access the building.
Riga – Latvia RPR	Aesthetics considering that it is a cultural-historical building, the most important thing would be to protect its cultural-historical and aesthetic properties; The most important is sustainability; sustainability is key, as the building should be preserved for future generations.
Gdynia – Poland FASADA	Respondent 1 answered that a future vision for the building centered around inclusion and sustainability could include the following elements: ensuring universal accessibility and affordability for diverse communities through inclusive design and programming. Implementing energy-efficient systems, renewable sources, and sustainable materials to reduce environmental impact. Promoting biodiversity through green spaces and educating visitors on sustainable lifestyles. Celebrating cultural diversity while aligning with the NEB initiative's principles of sustainability, aesthetics, and inclusion; Respondent 2 mentioned that sustainability is the most important NEB value; Respondent 3 mentioned all aspects are equally important and respondent 4 mentioned aesthetics.
Valladolid – Spain CARTIF	The following values were mentioned as most important for the experts: Sustainability (motivated by administrative use and public ownership); Sustainability and aesthetics; Inclusion; aesthetics (a new experience for different groups in society, creating an open space) + inclusion (accessibility to a new public space available to society, welcoming all ages, different groups and artistic contributions).
Visby – Sweden UU	The first person answered this question that the most important challenge for Visby is to turn around gentrification; The second expert didn't provide an answer, the third expert mentioned that sustainability is most important. Person 4 said

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	that 'from world heritage standpoint, all three are important' and that 'there shouldn't be a compromise to make'.
Izmir – Türkiye IBB	Inclusion is the most important aspect, as the building does not cater to the needs of people with disabilities at the moment; sustainability and inclusion; Inclusion and aesthetics.

5. Future activities for co-created social engagement

Building on the participatory approaches established in previous phases of INHERIT, this chapter outlines **key future activities that will foster further co-created social engagement** within the project's pilot sites. The upcoming actions will focus on strengthening stakeholder involvement, integrating creative methodologies, and ensuring sustainable and inclusive heritage management.

This chapter is structured into three interconnected sub-chapters. Together, these sections present a **comprehensive framework for advancing participatory heritage practices, reinforcing the importance of co-creation, innovation, and inclusivity** in shaping the future of CH engagement within INHERIT.

5.1. Mapping societal enablers in pilot sites

Mapping societal enablers in pilot sites is essential for understanding the conditions that facilitate or hinder **stakeholder engagement, policy implementation, and long-term CH resilience**. Societal enablers include social actors, policies, financial mechanisms, and participatory processes that support **community-driven and sustainable interventions**. The mapping process aims to identify key factors that influence the success of CH initiatives while ensuring alignment with broader EU policies and governance frameworks. Given the timeline constraints, this analysis primarily relies on desk research, while qualitative insights will be integrated later in the project through participatory workshops.

The methodological approach consists of two key steps. First, **desk research and policy analysis** focus on reviewing EU policies, such as the **New European Bauhaus** and Green Deal, to identify policy-driven enablers. This process included identifying key social actors at local, regional, and EU levels, including public institutions, private stakeholders, and community groups, while also analysing governance models, financial instruments, and participatory practices to assess the enabling conditions for CH projects. Second, **participatory mapping through INHERIT Social Labs** will engage communities and stakeholders in identifying and validating local societal enablers.

The participatory workshops will have place during the third and fourth rounds of **Social Labs** and will put a stronger emphasis on **creativity and visibility**, targeting a broader audience beyond core stakeholders. The **third round of Social Labs**, scheduled by **September 2025**, will focus on structured discussions that incorporate creative engagement formats, such as **peer learning, oral history, citizen science, multimodal storytelling, and design thinking** will help co-create insights. To avoid redundancy with the first two rounds of Social Labs, which have already addressed several social

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needs through methods like the World Café, the upcoming workshops will prioritise **innovative event formats that broaden outreach and ensure fresh perspectives are integrated**.

The **fourth round of Social Labs**, expected by **September 2026**, will refine and validate the **mapping results** through collaborative sessions and **public presentation events** designed to **enhance visibility and foster wider stakeholder involvement**. These events will not only showcase key findings but also actively engage new participants through creative formats, thereby ensuring the results are effectively communicated and embedded into future planning and governance processes.

Initial desk research highlighted several key societal enablers that influence the transformation of CH sites. **Institutional support and policy alignment** are crucial in ensuring effective governance and cross-sector collaboration. **Community participation and social inclusion mechanisms** help citizens engage in decision-making, fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility. **Financial accessibility**, including public-private partnerships, EU funding, and community-led financing models, determines the feasibility of long-term interventions. **The integration of digital tools, 3D modelling, and participatory mapping technologies** provides new ways to visualise and communicate findings. **Regulatory flexibility** is also essential, as adaptive urban and heritage policies must balance conservation with innovation to accommodate evolving societal needs.

The integration of participatory workshops into societal enabler mapping ensures a bottom-up, **community-driven approach** that aligns with INHERIT's broader goal of **enhancing social accessibility and inclusiveness in CH sites**. By engaging local stakeholders and connecting community needs with broader policy frameworks, this process will contribute to a more **resilient, inclusive, and participatory CH ecosystem**. While this deliverable provides a conceptual and research-based foundation, the upcoming **Social Labs will be key to further developing and validating the mapping process** through innovative, creative engagement strategies tailored to diverse audiences. Notably, the role of **creativity in placemaking** is explored as a means to engage various stakeholders and drive meaningful social participation.

5.2. Creativity acts as a catalyst for placemaking social engagement

Creativity plays a vital role in placemaking by promoting **social engagement**, strengthening community identity, and enhancing the cultural and economic value of heritage sites. Within the INHERIT project, creative practices act as a driving force for participatory heritage management, enabling inclusive, dynamic, and locally relevant approaches to cultural preservation and regeneration. By fostering deeper public involvement, **creativity transforms heritage spaces into vibrant, living environments** that reflect the collective identity of their communities.

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Beyond aesthetic improvements, **creativity actively shapes social interactions and community dynamics**. It empowers local stakeholders to become active participants in heritage transformation processes rather than passive observers. This engagement is particularly important in historic environments undergoing adaptation, where balancing conservation needs with contemporary urban demands can present challenges. Creative interventions bridge this gap by fostering a sense of ownership and shared responsibility for heritage conservation. Moreover, creative placemaking serves as a tool to address broader social challenges, transforming heritage spaces into platforms for dialogue, intercultural exchange, and social inclusion.

Creativity-driven placemaking aligns closely with the principles of the **New European Bauhaus (NEB)**, which **emphasises aesthetics, sustainability, and togetherness** in urban and cultural development. Such approaches not only contribute to preserving the historical integrity of heritage sites but also support economic revitalization by attracting cultural tourism, creative industries, and local businesses. Additionally, creative methods help build the resilience of heritage sites through adaptive reuse and innovative management models.

As part of INHERIT's participatory framework, **creativity will be further integrated into Social Lab activities** and engagement initiatives across pilot sites, enabling communities to explore new ways of interacting with their heritage environments. Insights gained from these creative processes will inform broader, community-led heritage management strategies, illustrating how culture and artistic innovation can drive social cohesion and urban regeneration. By placing creativity at the heart of placemaking, INHERIT fosters more inclusive, engaging, and sustainable heritage transformations that respond to the evolving identities and needs of contemporary society.

Interactive experiences can play a key role in creating meaningful connections between people and places, making heritage more accessible and engaging. **Creative interventions provide valuable opportunities for co-creation**, allowing communities to shape their surroundings in ways that align with their values and aspirations. These approaches are particularly effective in fostering intergenerational dialogue, bringing together younger and older community members to reinterpret and revitalise historical narratives.

Creativity can, therefore, **significantly enhance Social Labs 3 and 4 by fostering engagement, inclusiveness, and innovative solutions** for CH preservation. These Labs provide a unique opportunity to implement creative approaches that encourage active community involvement and collaborative problem-solving.

In **Social Lab 3**, focused on **idea generation**, creativity could be harnessed through visual storytelling workshops, enabling participants to express their connections to heritage sites using photography, drawing, or collage. Facilitated discussions, supported by visual tools and interactive voting systems, could stimulate open dialogue and diverse perspectives. Role-playing exercises may help stakeholders explore heritage issues from multiple viewpoints, encouraging empathy and deeper

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understanding. Interactive mapping sessions could engage participants in reimagining the use and future of heritage spaces, while creative brainstorming techniques could spark innovative, locally relevant ideas.

In **Social Lab 4**, which focuses on **refining and presenting solutions**, creative methods could be employed to develop and implement heritage interventions. Design thinking workshops may help participants co-create solutions such as temporary installations, interactive visitor experiences, or enhanced signage. Community-generated ideas could be showcased through pop-up exhibitions, providing a platform for public feedback and reflection. Immersive technologies like augmented and virtual reality (AR and VR) could visualise proposed transformations, making future scenarios more tangible and relatable. Storytelling sessions could capture personal narratives about the impact of interventions, shared through videos or podcasts, while community events like heritage walks or cultural festivals could serve as engaging platforms to present Lab outcomes and celebrate local heritage.

Throughout both Labs, **creative facilitation techniques - incorporating music, visual aids, or tactile materials - can enhance participation and engagement**. Intergenerational activities may further strengthen local identity and build stronger community bonds. These creative approaches aim to make complex ideas more accessible, ensuring that solutions are inclusive, contextually appropriate, and have a lasting positive impact.

5.3. Design and expected outcome of further activities including the Lab Project

The further development of the INHERIT Social Labs is designed to **strengthen participatory heritage management** by fostering deeper engagement, refining methodologies, and ensuring the long-term sustainability of community-driven initiatives. **The upcoming activities will build upon previous Social Lab insights**, integrating stakeholder perspectives to shape a structured framework for co-creation, policy alignment, and innovative heritage solutions. **The evolution of the Social Labs will involve a combination of participatory methodologies, interactive engagement techniques, and the establishment of a dedicated Lab Project**, reinforcing INHERIT's commitment to inclusive and sustainable heritage transformation.

A core element of these activities focuses on **enhancing social accessibility and inclusiveness in CH sites**. This will be achieved through iterative engagement, including participatory workshops, community consultations, and interdisciplinary collaboration. **The third round of Social Labs will serve as a key milestone** in this process, incorporating creative and digital engagement tools to facilitate meaningful discussions among stakeholders. These workshops will explore mid-term concepts related to urban planning, cultural well-being, and tourism, ensuring that participatory approaches contribute to broader social and economic revitalization efforts. The findings from these

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discussions will inform the next phase of the Social Labs, ensuring continuity and coherence throughout the project's lifecycle.

A crucial component of the future activities is the **establishment of the Lab Project** (see Table 11), which will **translate Social Lab discussions into tangible, community-driven interventions**. The Lab Project will be structured in two phases. **The first phase will involve a targeted survey and thematic selection process**, allowing stakeholders to identify and prioritise key issues based on Social Lab discussions. The survey results will guide further project development. **The second phase will focus on implementation**, where selected topics will be transformed into small-scale, high-impact initiatives. These could take various forms, including public exhibitions, community workshops, participatory heritage mapping, or co-created cultural events that strengthen local ties to heritage sites.

Table 11: Lab Project ideas developed so far by the INHERIT pilots

Pilots	Lab Project ideas developed so far
REGEA, pilot in Jastrebarsko, Croatia	Not developed yet
ELLET, pilot in Athens, Greece	A guided student workshop following expert insights
RPR, pilot in Riga, Latvia	Environmental accessibility, innovative solutions for improving CH energy efficiency, and the use of renewable energy sources (RES) technologies
FASADA, pilot in Gdynia, Poland	Activities involving the local community, including joint planting of plants, care of greenery, preparation of small architecture during the execution phase, and encouraging care of the common space after project completion
CARTIF, pilot in Valladolid, Spain	Not developed yet
UU, pilot in Visby, Sweden	Not developed yet
IBB, pilot in Imzir, Türkiye	Currently under exploration: an activity with the idea of 'using the courtyard of the pilot building more efficiently', developing some nature-best solution designs and ideas that can temporarily be applied to the courtyard, to be conducted with the help of a group of university students from design departments.

Beyond immediate interventions, the Lab Project will also explore longer-term strategies, such as crowdfunding models, policy integration mechanisms, and stakeholder-driven sustainability plans.

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The fourth round of Social Labs will play a pivotal role in validating the Lab Project's outcomes, sharing lessons learned, and integrating findings into broader heritage governance frameworks. This phase will conclude with a **public presentation event**, where key insights, best practices, and replicable models will be showcased to ensure knowledge transfer and long-term impact.

The expected outcomes of these further activities include the **development of a scalable participatory framework that enhances social accessibility, community ownership, and resilience** in CH management. Integrating Social Labs and the Lab Project into local policy discussions will ensure that heritage interventions remain relevant and responsive to community needs. Additionally, the co-creation budget allocated to pilot partners will support stakeholder-driven project implementation, maximising impact and fostering long-term engagement.

By embedding co-creation, interdisciplinary collaboration, and participatory governance into the Social Labs, the INHERIT project will contribute to a **more inclusive and sustainable heritage ecosystem**. Through continued iteration, adaptive learning, and community-led experimentation, these activities will provide a **replicable model for future heritage initiatives**, ensuring that CH remains a living, evolving space that reflects the needs and aspirations of contemporary society.

6. Conclusion and outlook

This deliverable aimed to highlight the importance of active societal participation and its enabling conditions for the INHERIT project efforts in advancing socially inclusive and sustainable heritage-built environment transformations. Through an exploration of participatory models and by integrating the New European Bauhaus (NEB) framework, stakeholder engagement, and digital solutions, the project fosters creativity, advocating for the benefits of a holistic approach that integrates technological innovation, multidisciplinary collaboration, and community-driven approaches to CH preservation while enhancing energy efficiency and resilience.

The **interim findings** reinforce the idea that inclusive, community-driven approaches are key to ensuring that CH remains relevant, sustainable, and resilient in the face of contemporary challenges. In particular, the **takeaways from the INHERIT Social Labs** underscore the value of multi-stakeholder engagement in identifying challenges, co-designing solutions, fostering knowledge exchange, and demonstrating the effectiveness of co-creation processes in CH adaptation. The **first-phase application of the Social Life Cycle Analysis (S-LCA)** provides an additional layer of assessment, offering empirical insights into the social impact of INHERIT interventions across pilot sites, helping to define best practices and tailor future strategies.

Looking ahead, INHERIT will refine engagement strategies and **deepen the integration of NEB values**, ensuring that aesthetics, sustainability, and inclusion remain central to CH renovations. Future efforts will focus on **expanding the Social Labs to a broader audience**, enhancing their role as platforms for experimentation and dialogue, **and carrying on a locally specific Lab Project**. Other loops of S-LCA will be carried out to further assess socio-economic impacts and refine methodologies. Stakeholders will also have the opportunity to test digital solutions on site, backed by interactive tools and a decision-support framework to facilitate informed decision-making and optimise heritage management practices. Further activities will involve the pilot's areas in policy dialogues to foster cross-sectoral cooperation and stewardship of a balanced approach between heritage conservation, innovative interventions, and community well-being. Capacity-building initiatives and workshops for stakeholders will be implemented, and roadmaps to replicate and scale up best practices across Europe will be developed, ensuring long-term impact.

Through these initiatives, **INHERIT contributes to a forward-thinking European discourse on heritage conservation and sustainable adaptation**, demonstrating that socially inclusive and environmentally responsible practices are both feasible and impactful for the future of European heritage, setting a benchmark for integrated and participatory heritage governance.

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D2.2 Active societal participation & enabling conditions for the INHERIT heritage-built environment

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Other useful links

CLIC project (Circular Models Leveraging Investments in Cultural Heritage Adaptive Reuse): <https://www.clicproject.eu/>

Climate for Culture: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/226973/reporting>

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HeritageCare project (Management and Monitoring System for Preventive Conservation of Historical and Cultural Buildings): <https://interreg-sudoe.eu/en/proyectos/monitorising-preventive-conservation-of-historical-and-cultural-heritage/>

INHERIT Multi-Stakeholder Forum (MSF): <https://inheritproject.eu/multi-stakeholder-forum/>

LIFEBauhausingEurope: <https://gbcroatia.org/cases/lifebauhausingeurope/>

New European Bauhaus Initiative: https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/index_en

NEB local initiatives: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/whats-new/newsroom/30-03-2022-new-european-bauhaus-support-to-cities-for-local-initiatives_en

Re-sourcing commons: <https://stadtaufmoebeln.uni-ak.ac.at/re-sourcing-commons/>

ROCK (Regeneration and Optimisation of Cultural Heritage in Creative and Knowledge Cities): <https://rockproject.eu/>

Smart DeCARB: <https://interreg-hr-ba-me.eu/project/project-library/smart-decarb/>

UNESCO Culture for Development Indicators <https://www.unesco.org/creativity/en/activities/cdis>

